

Oxidative C-H Homocoupling of Push-Pull Benzothiazoles: An Atom-Economical Route to Highly Emissive Quadrupolar Arylamine-Functionalized 2,2'-Bibenzothiazoles with Enhanced Two-Photon Absorption

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1 General Experimental Details

All chemicals were used as received from commercial suppliers without purification, if not mentioned otherwise. Benzothiazole, benzothiazol-2(3*H*)-one, diphenyl sulfide, trimethylsilyl acetylene, aniline, trimethyl borate, Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂, Pd(PPh₃)₄, Pd(OAc)₂, Pd₂(dba)₃ and CuI were purchased from TCI Chemicals, *N*-iodosuccinimide, 4-bromotriphenylamine, 4-iodoanisole, 4-fluoronitrobenzene, bromobenzene, iodobenzene, BINAP, trifluoromethanesulfonic (triflic) acid and potassium *tert*-butoxide from Fluorochem Ltd., Cu(OAc)₂, Cs₂CO₃, POCl₃, KI, H₃PO₂, ReCl(CO)₅, *n*-BuLi, phenantroline, 3-chloroperoxybenzoic acid and all organic solvents from Acros Organics. Solvents for Pd-catalysed cross-coupling reactions were purified prior to the synthesis: tetrahydrofuran was distilled from Na/benzophenone, triethylamine from CaH₂. DMSO was dried using 4 Å molecular sieves. Commercially available Cu(OAc)₂ was dried under reduced pressure at 155 °C for 3 hours.

NMR spectra were recorded with Varian NMR System 600 (600 MHz for ¹H and 151 MHz for ¹³C) and Varian NMR System™ 300 (300 MHz for ¹H and 75 MHz for ¹³C) instruments. ¹H and ¹³C chemical shifts (δ) are given relative to tetramethylsilane, samples were prepared in CDCl₃ (¹H δ 7.26, ¹³C δ 77.0 ppm) or DMSO-*d*₆ (¹H δ 2.50, ¹³C δ 39.5 ppm). ¹⁵N chemical shifts were measured indirectly, via ¹H–¹⁵N long range correlation on a VARIAN INOVA 600 MHz NMR spectrometer working at 599.78 (¹H) and 60.78 MHz (¹⁵N) equipped with Varian 5 mm triple resonance probe ¹H{¹³C/¹⁵N} equipped with an Z-gradient coil. Unified chemical shift scale was used for ¹⁵N with nitromethane as a secondary standard (δ = 0.0 ppm; Ξ = 10.1367670).^[1]

UV-vis spectra were measured on Hewlett Packard 8452A Diode Array spectrophotometer and fluorescence spectra were measured on Shimadzu RF 6000 Spectrofluorophotometer.

IR spectra were measured on Agilent Technologies Cary 630 FTIR. Melting points were measured on Büchi Melting Point M-565.

Elemental analysis was performed on Vario Micro Cube.

Column chromatography was performed with Merck Silica Gel 60 (0.040–0.063 mm) and Merck Alumina 90 (neutral), respectively. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed with Merck plates (Silica Gel 60, F-254). Compounds were detected at 254 nm and 365 nm, respectively.

2 Synthesis of starting compounds

2.1 Synthesis of 6-iodobenzothiazole from benzothiazol-2(3H)-one

2.1.1 Iodination of benzothiazol-2(3H)-one with *N*-iodosuccinimide

Benzothiazol-2(3H)-one (10.0 g, 66 mmol) was dissolved in the sulfuric acid (200 mL) diluted with 10 mL of deionized water. *N*-Iodosuccinimide (18.6 g, 83 mmol) was added portionwise over 5 min at 0 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hours and then poured onto ice (600 g). The solid was filtered off, washed with water until neutral reaction of the filtrate, then with 5 % aqueous solution of Na₂S₂O₅, saturated aq. solution of NaHCO₃ and deionized water. The solid was dried under reduced pressure to obtain 6-iodobenzothiazol-2(3H)-one as a brownish solid (15.6 g, 85 %). *R_f* = 0.13 (SiO₂, hexanes/ethyl acetate = 6:1); **Mp** 222 – 223 °C (lit.^[2] mp 225 – 226 °C); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.18 (s, 1H), 7.71 (d, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.58 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 6.90 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.1, 135.3, 134.4, 130.8, 126.1, 113.0, 85.3.

2.1.2 Chlorination of 6-iodobenzothiazol-2(3H)-one

POCl₃ (80 mL) was added via syringe into an argon-flushed round-bottom flask equipped with a condenser and containing 6-iodobenzothiazol-2(3H)-one (10.0 g, 36 mmol). The reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 36 h. After consumption of the starting material (monitored by TLC), the mixture was cooled to room temperature and then added into 500 mL of vigorously stirred water in small portions over 30 min (the temperature throughout the addition was maintained under 40 °C). The precipitate formed was collected by filtration, dissolved in chloroform (250 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo* to obtain 2-chloro-6-iodo-benzothiazole as a white solid (9.33 g, 88 %). *R_f* = 0.71 (SiO₂, hexanes/ethyl acetate = 6:1); **Mp** 134 – 136 °C (lit.^[3] mp 135 –

137 °C). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.11 (d, *J* = 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.77 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.67 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H); ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.8, 150.3, 137.9, 135.9, 129.5, 124.3, 90.1.

2.1.3 Hydrodechlorination of 2-chloro-6-iodobenzothiazole

2-Chloro-6-iodobenzothiazole (9.315 g, 31.5 mmol) was dissolved in acetic acid (150 mL) and KI (15.7 g, 95 mmol) and H₃PO₂ (20 mL) were added. The mixture was heated to 80 °C for 45 min. After cooling to room temperature, the mixture was poured onto ice, neutralized with aqueous NaOH (20 %) and extracted with dichloromethane (3×100 mL). Combined organic layers were washed with 5 % aqueous solution of Na₂S₂O₅, water, brine and dried over Na₂SO₄ to afford 6-iodobenzothiazole as a white solid (7.94 g) in 97 % yield. *R*_f = 0.37 (SiO₂, hexanes/ethyl acetate = 6:1); **Mp** 77 – 79 °C (lit.^[4] mp 78 – 80 °C); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.91 (s, 1H), 8.30 (d, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.87 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 7.79 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 1.5 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.3, 152.7, 135.9, 135.3, 130.4, 125.1, 90.1.

2.2 Synthesis of benzothiazol-6-amine from benzothiazole

2.2.1 Nitration of benzothiazole with HNO₃/H₂SO₄

Benzothiazole (18.2 mL, 0.17 mol) was dissolved in concentrated H₂SO₄ (46 mL). The solution was cooled to 0 °C and fuming HNO₃ (18.2 mL) was added dropwise at such a rate to keep the temperature below 5 °C throughout the addition. After the addition was completed, the reaction mixture was stirred under cooling for 15 min and then at room temperature for an additional 2 h. Subsequently, the mixture was poured into ice-cold water (400 mL). The precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with cold water until the pH was neutral, and then crystallized from ethanol to give 6-nitrobenzothiazole as a white solid in 65 % yield (20.0 g). **Mp** 176 – 177 °C (lit.^[4] mp 176 – 177 °C); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.28 (s, 1H), 8.93 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 8.41 (dd, *J* = 9.0, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.26 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H).

2.2.2 Reduction of 6-nitrobenzothiazole with SnCl₂

6-Nitrobenzothiazole (20.0 g, 111 mmol, 1.0 eq) was suspended in a mixture of CHCl₃ (200 mL) and MeOH (100 mL). SnCl₂·2H₂O (90 g, 398.9 mmol, 3.6 eq) was added in one portion followed by MeOH (100 mL). The reaction mixture was heated to reflux over 3 h under an inert atmosphere. Then the reaction mixture was cooled to rt, poured to a crushed ice (1.5 L), basified with 10 M NaOH (500 mL) and DCM (300 mL) was added. The mixture was stirred 30 min at rt and after separation of phases, the aqueous phase was extracted with another DCM (2×250 mL). Combined organic (DCM) phases were washed with brine, dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and solvent removed under reduced pressure. The product was isolated as a yellow solid (15.3 g, 92 % yield). **Mp** 86 – 87 °C (lit.^[4] mp 86 – 87 °C); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.87 (s, 1H), 7.71 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 6.80 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 5.40 (s, 2H).

2.3 Synthesis of arylamine-functionalized phenylacetylenes

2.3.1 4-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)phenylacetylene

2.3.1.1 Synthesis of *N,N*-diphenyl-4-[(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl]aniline

4-Bromotriphenylamine (10 g, 30.8 mmol), CuI (295 mg, 1.54 mmol) and $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (1.424 g, 1.232 mmol) were dissolved in dry toluene (50 mL) under inert atmosphere and dry triethylamine (52 mL) was added. Then trimethylsilylacetylene (6.6 mL, 46.2 mmol) was added and the mixture was heated to 80°C (in an oil bath) under inert atmosphere for 36 hours. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was cooled to rt and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes) to give the desired product as an orange solid (6.17 g) in 59 % yield. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.26 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 4H), 7.10 – 7.07 (m, 4H), 7.06 – 7.03 (m, 2H), 6.95 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 0.23 (s, 9H). $^1\text{H NMR}$ shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [5].

2.3.1.2 Synthesis of 4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylacetylene

N,N-Diphenyl-4-[(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl]aniline (6.17 g, 18.1 mmol) and potassium carbonate (24.96 g, 18.1 mmol) were dissolved in MeOH (100 mL) and THF (100 mL) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours. Then, insoluble K_2CO_3 was filtered off and organic solvents evaporated under reduced pressure. Purification by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes / ethyl acetate 9:1) afforded the desired arylacetylene as a yellow solid (3.02 g) in 62 % yield. R_f 0.48 (SiO_2 , hexanes/ CHCl_3 =4:1); Mp $80 - 82^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.^[4] $80 - 82^\circ\text{C}$) $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.34 – 7.32 (m, 2H), 7.29 – 7.25 (m, 4H), 7.11 – 7.09 (m, 4H), 7.07 – 7.04 (m, 2H), 6.97 – 6.95 (m, 2H), 3.02 (s, 1H). $^1\text{H NMR}$ shifts match those reported previously in ref. [4].

2.3.2 4-[*N,N*-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylacetylene

2.3.2.1 Synthesis of *N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline

1-Iodo-4-methoxybenzene (20 g, 85.46 mmol), aniline (3.8 mL, 40.7 mmol), CuI (1.55 g, 8.14 mmol), 1,10-phenanthroline (1.47 g, 8.14 mmol) and *tert*-BuOK (36.5 g, 325.6 mmol) were dissolved in dry toluene (250 mL) under argon atmosphere. Reaction mixture was heated to reflux in an oil bath for 16 hours. After cooling to rt, the reaction mixture was quenched with water (250 mL) and extracted with dichloromethane (3×250 mL). Organic phase was washed with brine (200 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude solid was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes / dichloromethane 1:1) affording the desired product as a yellow solid (4.9 g) in 40 % yield. *R_f* 0.2 (SiO₂, hexanes/DCM=1:1); **Mp** 105 – 106 °C (lit.^[6] 104 – 106 °C). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.16 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.03 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H), 6.95 – 6.91 (m, 2H), 6.87 – 6.83 (m, 1H), 6.81 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 4H), 3.78 (s, 6H).

2.3.2.2 Synthesis of 4-iodo-*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline

N,N-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline (6.40 g, 20.96 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of chloroform (25 mL) and acetic acid (25 mL). Then *N*-iodosuccinimide (4.72 g, 20.96 mmol) was added portionwise to reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hours, then quenched with water (50 mL) and extracted using chloroform (3×30 mL). Organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ and solvents removed under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes / dichloromethane 1:1) affording the product as a yellow solid (7.60 g) in 84 % yield. *R_f* 0.23 (SiO₂, hexanes/DCM=1:1); **Mp** 113-115 °C (lit.^[7] 114-116 °C) ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.05– 7.01 (m, 4H), 6.84 – 6.81 (m, 4H), 6.67 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.79 (s, 6H).

2.3.2.3 Synthesis of *N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-[(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl]aniline

4-Iodo-*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline (0.5 g, 1.16 mmol), CuI (11 mg, 0.058 mmol) and PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂ (41 mg, 0.058 mmol) were dissolved in dry triethylamine (7 mL) under argon. Then trimethylsilylacetylene (0.25 mL, 1.74 mmol) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred under inert atmosphere for 30 minutes. After this time, the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure, the solid residue suspended in chloroform (10 mL) and filtered through a short pad of silica. The desired product was obtained upon evaporation of chloroform under reduced pressure as a yellow solid (451 mg) in 97 % yield. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 7.04 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 4H), 6.83 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 4H), 6.79 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 3.79 (s, 6H), 0.22 (s, 9H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [8].

2.3.2.4 Synthesis of 4-[*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylacetylene

N,N-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-[(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl]aniline (451 mg, 1.123 mmol) and potassium carbonate (233 mg, 1.686 mmol) were dissolved in a mixture of methanol (10 mL) and tetrahydrofuran (5 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour, then filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes / dichloromethane 1:1) affording the desired arylacetylene as a yellow solid (278 mg) in 75 % yield. *R*_f 0.3 (SiO₂, hexanes/DCM=1:1); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.26 (s, 2H), 7.07 – 7.04 (m, 4H), 6.85 – 6.82 (m, 4H), 6.80 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 3.79 (s, 6H), 2.98 (s, 1H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [8].

2.4 Synthesis of arylamine-functionalized phenylboronic acids

2.4.1 4-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)phenylboronic acid

4-Bromotriphenylamine (10.0 g, 30.8 mmol) was dissolved in dry THF (60 mL). The mixture was cooled to -80 °C and then 2.5 M *n*-BuLi in THF (14.8 mL, 37.1 mmol) was added dropwise at -80 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred additional 2 h at -80 to -60 °C, then cooled to -80 °C and trimethyl borate (5.2 mL, 46.3 mmol) was added dropwise. Then the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature, quenched with 2M HCl (46 mL) and stirred 20 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was extracted with DCM (3 × 75 mL), washed with brine (50 mL), dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified using column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 4:1) affording the desired product as a white solid in 57 % yield. *R_f* 0.25 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=4:1); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.01 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.29 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 7.3 Hz, 4H), 7.18 – 7.13 (m, 4H), 7.11 – 7.06 (m, 4H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [9].

2.4.2 4-[*N,N*-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylboronic acid

4-Iodo-*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline (4.1 g, 9.51 mmol; see section 2.3.2.2) was dissolved in dry THF (30 mL). The mixture was cooled to -80 °C and then 1.6 M *n*-BuLi in hexanes (8.9 mL, 14.3 mmol) was added dropwise at -80 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred additional 2 h at -80 to -60 °C, then cooled to -80 °C and trimethyl borate (2.1 mL, 19.0 mmol) was added dropwise. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature, then quenched with 2 M HCl (19 mL) and stirred for 20 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was extracted with DCM (3 × 40 mL), washed with brine (30 mL), dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and

concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified using column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 3:1) affording the desired product as a white solid in 41 % yield. R_f 0.2 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=3:1); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.94 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.13 – 7.10 (m, 4H), 6.93 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 6.87 – 6.85 (m, 4H), 3.81 (s, 6H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [10].

3 Synthesis of arylamine-functionalized 2-H-benzothiazoles

3.1 6-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)benzothiazole (btz-I)

3.1.1 Method A - Arylation of benzothiazol-6-amine with trifenyliodonium triflate

3.1.1.1 Synthesis of diphenyliodonium triflate

A flame-dried flask was charged with dry dichloromethane (1 L) under argon atmosphere and iodobenzene (32.8 mL, 297 mmol) was added. Then, 75% 3-chloroperoxybenzoic acid (74.46 g, 324 mmol) was added in several portions. After 10 min of stirring, benzene (34.1 mL, 383 mmol) was added and the mixture was cooled to 0 °C. Triflic acid (78 mL, 883 mmol) was added during 1 h at 0 °C and the mixture was stirred additional 1 h at room temperature. The mixture was poured into diethyl ether (2 L), cooled to 0 °C and stirred 10 min. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with diethyl ether (2×250 mL) and dried under reduced pressure. The product was obtained as a white crystalline solid (76.67 g, 60%). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.25 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 4H), 7.67 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.54 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 4H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [11].

3.1.1.2 Synthesis of triphenylsulfonium triflate

Diphenyliodonium triflate (21.36 g, 49.7 mmol) was dissolved in dry chlorobenzene (420 mL) under argon atmosphere. Diphenyl sulfide (13.9 mL, 74.48 mmol) was added, followed by addition of CuI (472 mg, 2.48 mmol, 0.05 eq). The reaction mixture was heated to 105 °C in tightly closed flask overnight. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into hexanes (1 L) and stirred 10 min. The product was filtered off, washed with hexanes (2×200 mL), dissolved in CHCl₃ and filtered again. Organic solvent was removed under reduced pressure, affording triphenylsulfonium triflate (19.1 g, 93%) as a light brown solid. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.75-7.79 (m, 3H), 7.68-7.75 (m, 12H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [12].

3.1.1.3 Synthesis of 6-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)benzothiazole (btz-1)

Benzothiazol-6-amine (4.8 g, 32.0 mmol, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in dry toluene (500 mL) under argon atmosphere, cooled to -40°C , followed by addition of triphenylsulfonium triflate (29.0 g, 70.3 mmol, 2.2 eq) and *tert*-BuOK (8.6 g, 76.7 mmol, 2.4 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred for additional 2 h at -40°C , then cooling bath was removed and the reaction was stirred at rt overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into water (600 mL) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×200 mL). Combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , filtered and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate – 10:1 to 8:2) affording the desired product as a sandy-coloured solid (2.85 g, 30%). R_f 0.26 (SiO_2 , hexanes/EA=10:1 to 8:2); **Mp** 159 – 160 $^\circ\text{C}$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 9.24 (s, 1H), 7.98 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.32 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.5$ Hz, 4H), 7.18 (dd, $J = 8.8, 2.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.06 (dd, 2H, $J = 7.5$), 7.04 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 6H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 155.3, 149.5, 147.8, 145.6, 135.5, 130.1, 124.3, 124.0, 123.7, 123.6, 117.2. **Anal. Calcd** for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{S}$: C, 75.47; H, 4.67; N, 9.26. Found: C, 75.55; H, 4.65; N, 9.31. **IR (ATR)**: ν 2113 (w), 1582 (s), 1490 (s), 1469 (s), 1290 (s), 1273 (s), 867 (s), 841 (s), 754 (s) cm^{-1} .

3.1.2 Method B – Arylation of benzothiazol-6-amine with 4-fluoronitrobenzene

3.1.2.1 Synthesis of 6-[*N,N*-bis(4-nitrophenyl)amino]benzothiazole

Benzothiazol-6-amine (8.95 g, 59.6 mmol) and CsF (22.63 g, 149 mmol) were placed in a dried flask, the mixture was dried under reduced pressure for 30 min and the flask was filled with argon. Dry DMSO (100 mL) was added, followed by 4-fluoronitrobenzene (17.1 mL, 131.1 mmol) and the mixture was heated to 130°C in an oil bath for 16 h. After this time, the cooled reaction mixture was slowly poured into water (1.5 L). To remove unreacted 4-fluoronitrobenzene from

the precipitated product, a mixture of *i*-hexane and ethyl acetate (300 mL, 10/1) was added and after thorough stirring, organic layer was discarded. This procedure was repeated 3 more times, each time using 200 mL of *i*-hexane/ethyl-acetate mixture (10/1). The water layer containing solid residue was filtered and the precipitate washed with water. The obtained solid was dissolved in DCM and filtered. The crude product was precipitated by addition of hexane to filtrate. Solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the solid residue was purified by crystallization from hexanes/ethyl acetate affording the product as a bright-orange solid (19.04 g, 81 % yield). **Mp** 217.6 – 219 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 9.43 (s, 1H), 8.18 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 4H), 8.15 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.41 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.24 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 4H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 158.1, 152.1, 152.1, 142.6, 142.3, 136.0, 126.5, 126.1, 125.1, 123.1, 122.1. **Anal. Calcd** for C₁₉H₁₂N₄O₄S: C, 58.16; H, 3.08; N, 14.28. Found: C, 58.40; H, 3.20; N, 14.12. **IR (ATR)**: ν 3077 (w), 1730 (w), 1578 (s), 1491 (s), 1295 (s), 1278 (s), 1106 (s), 842 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.1.2.2 Synthesis of 6-[*N,N*-bis(4-aminophenyl)amino]benzothiazole

6-[*N,N*-bis(4-nitrophenyl)amino]benzothiazole (8.0 g, 20.4 mmol) was suspended in MeOH (350 mL) under argon atmosphere and 10 % palladium on carbon (2.17 g, 2.04 mmol) was added. Argon atmosphere was removed by reduced pressure and exchanged for H₂ (this exchange was repeated 3 times). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature under H₂ atmosphere for 7 days, then filtered through Celite and washed with MeOH. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure, the solid residue dissolved in DCM and filtered to get rid of inorganic solids. DCM from filtrate was removed under reduced pressure and the product was isolated as a brown powder (6.53 g, 99 % yield). **Mp** 165 – 166.8 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.96 (s, 1H), 7.73 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H), 7.10 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.83 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 4H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 4H), 5.00 (s, 4H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 151.8, 148.6, 146.3, 146.3, 136.3, 135.4, 127.8, 123.1, 117.7, 115.3, 108.4. **Anal. Calcd** for C₁₉H₁₆N₄S: C, 68.65; H, 4.85; N, 16.85. Found: C, 68.69; H, 4.85; N, 16.93. **IR (ATR)**: ν 3329 (w), 3207 (w), 1595 (m), 1501 (s), 1464 (s), 1260 (s), 822 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.1.2.3 Hydrodeamination of 6-[N,N-bis(4-aminophenyl)amino]benzothiazole

To a stirred solution of *tert*-butyl nitrite (2.74 mL, 20.70 mmol) in dry THF (45 mL) at 60 °C was added dropwise (over the course of 30 min) a solution of benzothiazol-6-amine (3.277 g, 9.86 mmol) in dry THF (45 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred 45 min at 60 °C, then 50% aq. solution of H₃PO₂ (20.5 ml, 197 mmol) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for additional 24 h at 60 °C. After cooling to rt, the reaction mixture was poured to a mixture of water (300 mL) and brine (100 mL), basified with 1 M NaOH (300 mL) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×200 mL). Combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude solid was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate – 10:1 to 8:2) affording the desired product as a sandy-coloured solid (1.18 g, 39%). **R_f** 0.25 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=10:1 to 8:2); **Mp** 159 – 160 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 9.24 (s, 1H), 7.98 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.32 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 7.5 Hz, 4H), 7.18 (dd, *J* = 8.8, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.06 (dd, 2H, *J* = 7.5), 7.04 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 155.3, 149.5, 147.8, 145.6, 135.5, 130.1, 124.3, 124.0, 123.7, 123.6, 117.2. **Anal. Calcd** for C₁₉H₁₄N₂S: C, 75.47; H, 4.67; N, 9.26. Found: C, 75.55; H, 4.65; N, 9.31. **IR (ATR):** ν 2113 (w), 1582 (s), 1490 (s), 1469 (s), 1290 (s), 1273 (s), 867 (s), 841 (s), 754 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.2 Buchwald-Hartwig cross-coupling reactions

3.2.1 Benzothiazol-6-amine with bromobenzene and Cs₂CO₃ as a base

A flame-dried flask was charged with benzothiazol-6-amine (1.0 g, 3.9 mmol), BINAP (122 mg, 0.2 mmol), Pd(OAc)₂ (35 mg, 0.2 mmol) and Cs₂CO₃ (3.812 g, 11.7 mmol) under argon and dry 1,4-dioxane (30 mL) was added. Subsequently, bromobenzene (1.0 mL, 9.8 mmol) was added under stirring and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux over 48 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with dichloromethane (3×50 mL). Combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified using column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 4:1) affording *N*-phenylbenzothiazol-6-amine (0.46 g, 52%) as a light-yellow solid as the major product. *R*_f 0.32 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=4:1); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.79 (s, 1H), 7.99 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.61 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.29–7.33 (m, 2H), 7.20 (dd, *J* = 8.8, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.12 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 6.98–7.02 (m, 1H), 5.88 (s, 1H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [13]. Besides we isolated trace amounts of *N*,2-diphenylbenzothiazol-6-amine as the minor product (see also the procedure below).

3.2.2 Benzothiazol-6-amine with bromobenzene and *t*BuOK as a base

A flame-dried flask was charged with benzothiazol-6-amine (0.5 g, 1.95 mmol), BINAP (60.8 mg, 0.10 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃ (71.5 mg, 0.08 mmol) and potassium *tert*-butanolate (0.66 g, 5.86 mmol) under argon atmosphere and dry toluene (20 mL) was added. Bromobenzene (0.51 mL, 4.88 mmol) was added under stirring and the mixture was heated to reflux over 48 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 mL). Combined organic phases were washed with brine (20 mL), dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified / separated using column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 4:1).

***N*-Phenylbenzothiazol-6-amine**

(103 mg, 24 %, light yellow solid) $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.79 (s, 1H), 7.99 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.61 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.29-7.33 (m, 2H), 7.20 (dd, $J = 8.8, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.12 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 6.98-7.02 (m, 1H), 5.88 (s, 1H). $^1\text{H NMR}$ shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [13].

***N,2*-Diphenylbenzothiazol-6-amine**

(118 mg, 20 %, light yellow solid) $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.04 (dd, $J = 7.9, 1.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.94 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.57 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.47 (m, 3H), 7.32 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.17 (dd, $J = 8.7, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.14 (dd, $J = 8.5, 0.9$ Hz, 2H), 7.00 (dd, $J = 7.5, 0.9$ Hz, 1H), 5.87 (br s, 1H). $^1\text{H NMR}$ shifts match those reported for this compound in ref. [14].

2-Phenylbenzothiazol-6-amine

(traces, yellow oil) $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.00–8.03 (m, 2H), 7.84 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.42–7.48 (m, 3H), 7.14 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.85 (dd, $J = 8.6, 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.85 (br s, 2H).

3.3 6-[4-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)phenyl]benzothiazole (**btz-II**)

A mixture of 6-iodobenzothiazole (1.0 g, 3.8 mmol), 4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylboronic acid (1.32 g, 4.56 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.88 g, 0.76 mmol) was dissolved in toluene (30 mL), ethanol (10 mL) and potassium carbonate (1.6 g, 11.4 mmol) dissolved in water (1 mL) was added under argon atmosphere. The reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 12 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and purified using column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 4:1) to give **btz-II** as a yellow solid (1.05 g, 73 % yield). *R*_f 0.2 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=4:1); *Mp* 173 – 174 °C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.97 (s, 1H), 8.16 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 8.12 (d, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.53 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.28 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 4H), 7.16 (t, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 6H), 7.05 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.7, 152.2, 147.5, 138.6, 134.5, 134.1, 129.3, 128.1, 125.5, 124.6, 123.7, 123.6, 123.1, 119.5. **Anal. Calcd** for C₂₅H₁₈N₂S: C, 79.33; H, 4.79; N, 7.40. Found: C, 79.44; H, 4.71; N, 7.29. **IR (ATR):** ν 2959 (w), 2921 (w), 1584 (s), 1509 (s), 1486 (s), 1259 (s), 813 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.4 6-[4-[*N,N*-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenyl]benzothiazole (**btz-III**)

A dried flask was charged with 6-iodobenzothiazole (0.91 g, 3.5 mmol), 4-[*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylboronic acid (1.29 g, 3.68 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.81 g, 0.7 mmol), and then flushed with argon. Degassed solution of K₂CO₃ (1.453 g, 10.51 mmol) in water (5.3 mL) was added, followed by addition of a degassed mixture of toluene (20 mL) and EtOH (8 mL). The reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 30 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with dichloromethane (3×15 mL). Combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes / ethyl acetate = 10:1) affording **btz-III** as a yellow solid (0.91 g, 60 % yield). *R*_f 0.2 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=10:1); *Mp* 55 – 57 °C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.14 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 8.09 (d, *J* = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 7.71 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 7.46 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.10 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 4H), 7.01 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 6.85 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 4H), 3.80 (s, 6H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.2, 153.7, 152.2, 148.7, 140.9, 139.0, 134.7, 132.2, 128.0, 126.9, 125.6, 123.7, 120.7, 119.4, 115.0, 55.7, 55.7. **Anal. Calcd** for C₂₇H₂₂N₂O₂S: C, 73.95; H, 5.06; N, 6.39. Found: C, 74.09; H, 5.06; N, 6.37. **IR (ATR):** ν 2996 (w), 2831 (w), 1500 (s), 1462 (s), 1236 (s), 1032 (s), 825 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.5 6-[4-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)phenylethynyl]benzothiazole (**btz-IV**)

6-Iodobenzothiazole (1.0 g, 3.88 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂ (403 mg, 0.575 mmol) and CuI (55 mg, 0.287 mmol) were dissolved under argon atmosphere in a mixture of dry THF (14 mL) and dry Et₃N (8.6 mL). The mixture was stirred 15 min at room temperature, then 4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylacetylene (1.149 g, 4.268 mmol) in THF (8 mL) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture under inert atmosphere was stirred overnight at room temperature. Then the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 9:1) providing **btz-IV** as a white solid (1.16 g, 75%). *R_f* 0.22 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=9:1); *Mp* 184 – 186 °C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.01 (s, 1H), 8.11 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.08 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 7.64 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.39 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.28 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 7.4 Hz, 4H), 7.12 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.1 Hz, 4H), 7.07 (dd, *J* = 7.4, 1.1 Hz, 2H), 7.02 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.9, 152.8, 148.3, 147.3, 134.1, 132.8, 129.9, 129.6, 125.3, 125.0, 123.8, 123.6, 122.4, 121.4, 115.8, 91.0, 88.3. **Anal. Calcd** for C₂₇H₁₈N₂S: C, 80.57; H, 4.51; N, 6.96. Found: C, 80.50; H, 4.43; N, 6.90. **IR (ATR):** ν 2875 (w), 2362 (w), 1684 (s), 1477 (s), 1437 (s), 1196 (s), 1106 (s), 1067 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.6 6-{4-[*N,N*-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylethynyl}benzothiazole (**btz-V**)

6-Iodobenzothiazole (0.50 g, 1.92 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂ (80 mg, 0.115 mmol) and CuI (7.3 mg, 0.038 mmol) were dissolved under argon atmosphere in dry THF (10 mL) and dry Et₃N (2.7 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred 15 min at room temperature, then 4-[*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylacetylene (742 mg, 1.92 mmol) in THF (4 mL) was added dropwise and the mixture under inert atmosphere was stirred overnight at room temperature. Then the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid residue was purified using column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: hexanes/ethyl acetate = 9:1) affording **btz-V** as a yellow solid (0.63 g, 71 % yield). *R_f* 0.15 (SiO₂, hexanes/EA=9:1); *Mp* 59 – 61 °C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 9.00 (s, 1H), 8.10 (d, *J* = 0.9 Hz, 1H), 8.07 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 7.63 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.08 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 4H), 6.86 (dd, *J* = 8.9, 2.5 Hz, 6H), 3.81 (s, 6H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.4, 154.6, 149.0, 140.1, 132.5, 129.6, 127.2, 124.7, 123.4, 121.5, 119.5, 114.8, 113.4, 91.2, 87.5, 55.5. **Anal. Calcd** for

C₂₉H₂₂N₂O₂S: C, 75.30; H, 4.79; N, 6.06. Found: C, 75.35; H, 4.83; N, 6.16. **IR (ATR):** ν 1587 (s), 1499 (s), 1320 (s), 1285 (s), 1236 (s), 1030 (s), 824 (s) cm⁻¹.

3.7 (E)-6-[4-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)phenylethenyl]benzothiazole (**btz-VI**)

To a solution of 4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylacetylene (0.7 g, 2.6 mmol) in THF (6 mL) was added catecholborane (0.33 mL, 3.12 mmol) under an atmosphere of nitrogen and the solution was heated to reflux. After 1.5 h an additional amount of catecholborane (0.28 mL, 2.6 mmol) was added and heating was continued for further 2 h. After cooling to rt, a solution of 6-iodobenzothiazole (0.564 g, 2.16 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.499 mg, 0.432 mmol) in THF (6 mL) was added dropwise, and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. Consequently, 20% aqueous solution of Na₂CO₃ (2.6 mL) was added slowly and the mixture was heated to reflux for 20 h. After this time, the reaction mixture was cooled, quenched with water (20 mL), and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×30 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with water, brine and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Organic solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure and the solid residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: ethyl acetate/hexanes = 1:9) affording **btz-VI** as a yellow solid (0.52 g, 60 % yield). **R_f** 0.2 (SiO₂, EA/hexanes=1:9); **Mp** 59 – 60 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.10 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 8.04 (d, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.70 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.29 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.19 – 7.03 (m, 12H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 153.7, 152.6, 147.7, 147.5, 135.6, 134.6, 131.0, 129.3, 129.3, 127.4, 126.1, 124.6, 124.6, 123.6, 123.4, 123.2, 119.4. **Anal. Calcd** for C₂₇H₂₀N₂S: C, 80.17; H, 4.98; N, 6.93. Found: C, 80.35; H, 5.10; N, 7.23. **IR (ATR):** ν 3021 (w), 2922 (w), 1585 (s), 1506 (s), 1487 (s), 1324 (s), 1273 (s), 752 (s) cm⁻¹.

4 Oxidative homocoupling of 2-H-benzothiazoles

4.1 Synthesis of 2,2'-bibenzothiazole

Method A: Benzothiazole (8.07 mL, 0.074 mol) was dissolved in nitrobenzene (20 mL) and the mixture was heated to 215°C. Cu(OAc)_2 (13.44 g, 0.074 mol) – dried prior to the synthesis under reduced pressure at 155°C for 3 hours – was added portionwise over the course of 12 min and after complete addition the reaction mixture was heated for another 3 min. Subsequently, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, filtered and the slurry washed with hot saturated solution of EDTA in water (300 mL) and then with 93% ethanol (100 mL) to give 2,2'-bibenzothiazole as a gold-yellow solid (7.4 g) in 75% yield.

Method B: Benzothiazole (8.07 mL, 0.074 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of xylenes (50 mL) and the mixture was heated to reflux. Then Cu(OAc)_2 (13.44 g, 0.074 mmol) – dried prior to the synthesis under reduced pressure at 155°C for 3 hours – was added portionwise and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 3 hours. After cooling to room temperature, the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid was triturated with 26 % aqueous solution of ammonia. The precipitate was filtered under reduced pressure and washed with cold 96% ethanol to afford 2,2'-bibenzothiazole as a gold-yellow solid (7.0 g) in 70 % yield.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.17 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.99 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H), 7.57 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.50 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H). **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 161.5, 153.6, 135.9, 126.8, 126.6, 124.1, 122.0.

4.2 Homocoupling of arylamine-functionalized 2-H-benzothiazoles – general procedure

Given arylamine-functionalized 2-H-benzothiazole (2 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of xylenes (20 mL), heated to reflux and Cu(OAc)₂ (1.0 equivalent) was added portionwise over the course of 10 minutes [note: Cu(OAc)₂ was dried under reduced pressure at 155°C for 3 hours]. After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 2–3 hours. Then the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure, slurry dissolved in dichloromethane (60 mL), the organic layer washed with hot saturated aq. solution of disodium EDTA (60 mL), brine (30 mL) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Organic solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the solid residue purified by column chromatography or crystallized.

4.2.1 6,6'-Bis(*N,N*-diphenylamino)-2,2'-bibenzothiazole (bisbtz-I)

(yellow solid) Eluent: hexanes / CHCl₃ 1:1; (SiO₂, R_f = 0.18), yield: 0.43 g (72 %). **Mp** 295 – 297 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.93 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 7.53 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 2H), 7.34 – 7.28 (m, 8H), 7.27 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.26 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 7.15 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 8H), 7.10 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 4H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 159.5, 149.1, 147.4, 147.0, 137.2, 129.5, 124.9, 124.1, 123.7, 123.3, 114.7. **¹⁵N NMR** (61 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -279.3, -69.8. **Anal. Calcd** for C₃₈H₂₆N₄S₂: C, 75.72; H, 4.35; N, 9.30. Found: C, 75.53; H, 4.39; N, 9.40. **IR (ATR):** ν 2924 (w), 2115 (w), 1583 (s), 1484 (s), 1468 (s), 1269 (s), 753 (s), 694 (s) cm⁻¹.

4.2.2 6,6'-Bis[4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenyl]-2,2'-bibenzothiazole (bisbtz-II)

(orange solid) Crystallized from chloroform and hexanes, yield: 0.51 g (68 %). **Mp** 276 – 278 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.17 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 8.15 (d, *J* = 1.9 Hz, 2H), 7.77 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 1.9 Hz, 2H), 7.56 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 7.31 – 7.28 (m, 8H), 7.17 (t, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 12H), 7.08 – 7.05 (m, 4H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.2, 152.6, 147.8, 147.5, 139.5, 136.7, 133.7, 129.4, 128.1, 126.1, 124.7, 124.1, 123.6, 123.2, 119.4. **Anal. Calcd** for C₅₀H₃₄N₄S₂: C, 79.55; H, 4.54; N, 7.42. Found: C, 79.77; H, 4.43; N, 7.27. **IR (ATR):** ν 2331 (w), 2126 (w), 1922 (w), 1587 (s), 1489 (s), 1326 (s), 1268 (s), 815 (s) cm⁻¹.

4.2.3 6,6'-Bis{4-[N,N-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenyl}-2,2'-bibenzothiazole (bisbtz-III)

(red solid) Eluent: hexanes / CHCl₃ 4:1 (SiO₂, **R_f** = 0.2), yield: 0.84 g (96 %). **Mp** 279 – 281 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.15 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 8.11 (d, *J* = 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.75 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 1.7 Hz, 2H), 7.50 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 8H), 7.02 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 6.86 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 8H), 3.82 (s, 12H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.0, 156.1, 152.4, 149.1, 140.6, 139.7, 136.7, 131.6, 127.8, 126.8, 126.0, 124.0, 120.8, 119.1, 115.1, 55.5. **Anal. Calcd** for C₅₄H₄₂N₄O₄S₂: C, 74.12; H, 4.84; N, 6.40. Found: C, 74.32; H, 4.50; N, 6.47. **IR (ATR):** ν 2355 (w), 1591 (s), 1503 (m), 1460 (s), 1238 (s), 1104 (m), 1028 (s), 810 (s) cm⁻¹.

4.2.4 6,6'-Bis[4-(N,N-diphenylamino)phenylethynyl]-2,2'-bibenzothiazole (bisbtz-IV)

(orange solid) Eluent: hexanes / CHCl₃ 1:1 (SiO₂, **R_f** = 0.25), yield: 0.50 g (62 %). **Mp** 300 – 302 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.12 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 2H), 8.09 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.67 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.7 Hz, 2H), 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H), 7.31 – 7.28 (m, 8H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 8H), 7.08 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 4H), 7.02 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.9, 152.9, 148.3, 147.1, 136.1, 132.6, 130.4, 129.4, 125.1, 124.8, 123.8, 123.7, 122.4, 122.1, 115.4, 91.8, 88.2. **Anal. Calcd** for C₅₄H₃₄N₄S₂: C, 80.77; H, 4.27; N, 6.98. Found: C, 80.71; H, 4.42; N, 7.00. **IR (ATR):** ν 2920 (w), 2852 (w), 2360 (w), 2338 (w), 1581 (s), 1487 (s), 1285 (s), 817 (s) cm⁻¹.

4.2.5 6,6'-Bis{4-[*N,N*-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylethynyl}-2,2'-bibenzothiazole (bisbtz-V)

(orange solid) Eluent: hexanes / CHCl₃ 4:1 (SiO₂, **R_f** = 0.20), yield: 0.83 g (90 %). **Mp** 223 – 225 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.11 (d, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 8.07 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.65 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.3 Hz, 2H), 7.34 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 7.09

(d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 8H), 6.86 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 12H), 3.81 (s, 12H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.8, 157.2, 152.3, 149.1, 140.0, 136.1, 132.5, 130.3, 127.2, 124.6, 123.7, 119.0, 114.8, 113.2, 92.3, 55.5. **Anal. Calcd** for C₅₈H₄₂N₄O₄S₂: C, 75.47; H, 4.59; N, 6.07. Found: C, 75.41; H, 4.75; N, 5.98. **IR (ATR):** ν 2835 (w), 2341 (w), 2199 (w), 1585 (s), 1500 (s), 1283 (s), 1239 (s), 819 (s) cm⁻¹.

4.2.6 (*E,E*)-6,6'-[4-(*N,N*-Diphenylamino)phenylethenyl]-2,2'-bibenzothiazole (bisbtz-VI)

(red solid) Crystallized from DCM and hexanes, yield: 0.65 g (80 %). **Mp** 290 – 292 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.09 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 8.04 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 2H), 7.71 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 1.7 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz,

4H), 7.30 – 7.26 (m, 8H), 7.21 – 7.12 (m, 12H), 7.09 – 7.04 (m, 8H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.1, 153.0, 147.9, 147.5, 143.9, 136.8, 136.7, 130.6, 129.9, 129.3, 127.6, 125.9, 125.4, 124.7, 124.0, 123.3, 123.3, 119.2. **Anal. Calcd** for C₅₄H₃₈N₄S₂: C, 80.37; H, 4.75; N, 6.94. Found: C, 80.50; H, 4.71; N, 6.88. **IR (ATR):** ν 3021 (w), 2977 (w), 1583 (s), 1487 (s), 1324 (s), 1274 (s), 1174 (s), 794 (s) cm⁻¹.

5 Complexation of bisbtz-I with $\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_5$

A mixture of **bisbtz-I** (75 mg, 0.12 mmol) and rhenium pentacarbonyl chloride (45 mg, 0.12 mmol) was dissolved in dry toluene (5 mL) and heated to reflux for 1 h under an inert atmosphere. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and concentrated under reduced

pressure. The solid residue was dissolved in hot chloroform, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure, affording $\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_3(\text{bisbtz-I})$ as a dark purple solid (80 mg) in 75% yield. **Mp** > 220 °C. **^1H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.31 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.45 (dd, $J = 9.2, 2.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.42 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.37 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 8H), 7.21 – 7.18 (m, 12H). **^{13}C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 158.40, 149.32, 146.36, 145.51, 136.06, 129.89, 125.76, 125.07, 124.26, 124.21, 112.22. **^{15}N NMR** (61 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -274.6, -123.7. **Anal. Calcd** for $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{26}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_3\text{ReS}_2$: C, 55.06; H, 2.93; N, 4.90. Found: C, 55.12; H, 2.89; N, 4.73. **IR (ATR)**: ν 2016 (s), 1891 (s), 1578 (s), 1544 (s), 1544 (m), 1486 (s), 1467 (s), 1288 (s), 1258 (s), 693 (s) cm^{-1} .

6 NMR spectra of key intermediates and target 2,2'-bibenzothiazoles

¹H NMR spectrum of 6-iodobenzothiazol-2(3H)-one (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of 6-iodobenzothiazol-2(3H)-one (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 2-chloro-6-iodobenzothiazole (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of 2-chloro-6-iodobenzothiazole (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 6-iodobenzothiazole (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of 6-iodobenzothiazole (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 6-nitrobenzothiazole (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of benzothiazol-6-amine (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)

¹H NMR spectrum of 6-[*N,N*-bis(4-nitrophenyl)amino]benzothiazole (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)

¹³C NMR spectrum of 6-[*N,N*-bis(4-nitrophenyl)amino]benzothiazole (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)

**¹H NMR spectrum of 6-[*N,N*-bis(4-aminophenyl)amino]benzothiazole
(600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)**

**¹³C NMR spectrum of 6-[*N,N*-bis(4-aminophenyl)amino]benzothiazole
(151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)**

¹H NMR spectrum of diphenyliodonium triflate (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)

¹H NMR spectrum of triphenylsulfonium triflate (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of *N,N*-diphenyl-4-[(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl]aniline (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylacetylene (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of *N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo-*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

**¹H NMR spectrum of *N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-[(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl]aniline
(600 MHz CDCl₃)**

**¹H NMR spectrum of 4-[*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylacetylene
(600 MHz, CDCl₃)**

¹H NMR spectrum of 4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylboronic acid (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 4-[*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]phenylboronic acid (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of btz-I (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)

¹³C NMR spectrum of btz-I (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆)

¹H NMR spectrum of btz-II (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of btz-II (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of btz-III (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of btz-III (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of btz-IV (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of btz-IV (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of btz-V (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of btz-V (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of btz-VI (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of btz-VI (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of 2,2'-bibenzothiazole (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of 2,2'-bibenzothiazole (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of bisbtz-I (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of bisbtz-I (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

^{15}N NMR spectrum of bisbtz-I (61 MHz, CDCl_3)

¹H NMR spectrum of bisbtz-II (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of bisbtz-II (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of bisbtz-III (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of bisbtz-III (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of bisbtz-IV (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of bisbtz-IV (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of bisbtz-V (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of bisbtz-V (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹H NMR spectrum of bisbtz-VI (600 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C NMR spectrum of bisbtz-VI (151 MHz, CDCl₃)

^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_3(\text{bisbtz-I})$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{13}C NMR spectrum of $\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_3(\text{bisbtz-I})$ (151 MHz, CDCl_3)

^{15}N NMR spectrum of $\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_3(\text{bisbtz-1})$ (61 MHz, CDCl_3)

7 Synthesis of (*E,E*)-4,4'-[4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylethenyl]-2,2'-bipyridine

To a flask containing 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (0.50 g, 2.7 mmol) and potassium *tert*-butoxide (1.83 g, 16.3 mmol) under argon atmosphere, dry DMF (15 mL) was added through septum via syringe and the resulting mixture was heated to 70 °C in an oil bath for 1 h. Subsequently, the aldehyde (1.67 g, 6.1 mmol) was added as a solid and the resulting mixture was stirred at 70 °C for 4 hours. After cooling to RT, the mixture was poured into water and the solid collected by filtration. After drying, the product was purified by trituration with boiling methanol. The insoluble part was collected to yield the product as a yellow solid (1.07 g, 56 %). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.64 (d, *J* = 5.1 Hz, 2H), 8.51 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 2H), 7.43 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 4H), 7.37 (dd, *J* = 5.2, 1.8 Hz, 2H), 7.29 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 8H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 8H), 7.08 – 7.05 (m, 8H), 7.01 (d, *J* = 16.1 Hz, 4H). ¹H NMR shifts match those reported for this compound in refs. [41] and [42].

¹H NMR spectrum of (*E,E*)-4,4'-[4-(*N,N*-diphenylamino)phenylethenyl]-2,2'-bipyridine (bpy)
(600 MHz, CDCl₃)

8 UV-vis absorption and emission spectra

Figure S1. UV-Vis spectra of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene (measured at $c = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ M)

Figure S2. Normalized emission spectra of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene (measured at concentrations, at which the absorbance at the excitation wavelength < 0.1)

toluene solutions ($c = 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M)

Figure S3. Comparison of absorption and emission spectra of *push-pull* 2-H-benzothiazoles (**btz-IV**, **btz-VI**) and quadrupolar systems thereof (**bisbtz-IV**, **bisbtz-VI**), showing remarkable red-shifts of absorption and emission peaks and increase of extinction coefficients upon homocoupling of two heteroarenes (1×10^{-5} M solutions in toluene).

Figure S4. Emission spectra of **btz-VI** and **bisbtz-VI** in toluene and CHCl₃, demonstrating a pronounced red-shift of emission in **bisbtz-VI** dye upon increasing solvent polarity.

toluene solutions ($c = 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M)

Figure S5. Comparison of UV-vis absorption spectra of **bisbtz-I** and **ReCl(CO)₃(bisbtz-I)**
(toluene solutions, $c=1 \times 10^{-5}$ M)

9 Fluorescence quantum yields measurements and TCSPC spectroscopy

The fluorescence quantum yields were determined by means of the following model:^[15]

$$\Phi_x = \Phi_{ref} \left(\frac{grad_x}{grad_{ref}} \right) \left(\frac{\eta_x^2}{\eta_{ref}^2} \right)$$

where Φ is the fluorescence quantum yield, *grad* denotes the gradient from the plot of integrated fluorescence intensity (area under the emission curve) vs. absorbance, and η is the refractive index of the solvents used in measurement. The subscripts *ref* and *X* stand for the reference and tested dye, respectively.

A series of **btz** and **bisbtz** dye solutions in UV-VIS grade toluene ($\eta = 1.496$) or chloroform ($\eta = 1.445$) was prepared so that the absorbance at excitation wavelength ($\lambda_{exc} = 370$ nm for **btz** and $\lambda_{exc} = 410$ nm for **bisbtz**) did not exceed 0.1. The standard – perylene (QY, $\lambda_{exc} = 410$ nm; $\Phi_{ref} = 0.94$)^[16] was dissolved in cyclohexane ($\eta = 1.427$). Emission intensity (measured as area under emission curve) was plotted against absorbance at λ_{exc} and the slope obtained was used for quantum yield calculation. The quantum yields are summarized in Table 1 in the main text.

The time resolved fluorescence measurements were performed by means of Time Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) spectroscopy.^[17] The samples were excited at 400 nm using ps diode lasers and the detection was made under magic angle conditions. The Instrument's Response Function (IRF) of the system was ~ 80 ps.

Figure S6. Nanosecond fluorescence dynamics for the **bisbtz** dyes in toluene solution ($c = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ M). The excitation wavelength was 400 nm and the detection was at the wavelength of emission maxima.

Table S1. Fitting parameters for the nanosecond (ns) fluorescence dynamics for the **bisbtz** dyes in toluene solution ($c = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ M). The fitting was realized by a bi-exponential function taking into account the instrument's response function.

dye	λ_{det} (nm)	A_1	τ_1 (ns)	A_2	τ_2 (ns)	$\langle \tau \rangle$ (ns)
bisbtz-I	495	0.17	0.36	0.83	1.99	1.70
bisbtz-II	495	0.22	0.50	0.78	1.59	1.34
bisbtz-III	527	0.24	0.60	0.76	2.46	2.00
bisbtz-IV	496	0.21	0.47	0.79	1.42	1.22
bisbtz-V	527	0.23	0.65	0.77	2.30	1.92
bisbtz-VI	517	0.27	0.61	0.73	1.48	1.24

10 TPEF measurements

The two-photon absorption (TPA) properties of selected dyes were studied via a two-photon excited fluorescence (TPEF) technique using femtosecond (fs) pulsed excitation.^{[18]-[20]} A mode-locked Ti:Sapphire fs laser, emitting 80 fs pulses tunable from 730 to 870 nm with 80 MHz repetition frequency, has been used as the excitation source. The laser beam passed through a 5-fold expanding telescope in order to achieve uniform illumination at the back of the microscope objective lens (16-fold), used to focus the fs laser beam in the samples. The samples were measured in quartz cuvettes as 2×10^{-5} M solutions of the dyes in toluene. Three linear motorized stages (Newport) driven by a three-axis controller (Newport) have been utilized to move each sample towards the excitation focal point. The TPA-induced fluorescence has been collected backwards and was separated by the laser beam via a dichroic mirror with a high-pass region (cold mirror) and a set of filters. Finally, a photomultiplier connected to photon-counting electronics (Becker-Hickl) was used to detect the emitted fluorescence. Rhodamine 6G in MeOH (2×10^{-5} M) has been used as the reference sample while the measured scattering intensity from the solvent has been subtracted. The calculations of the TPA cross sections have been made after plotting the TPEF intensity as a function of the excitation intensity in order to confirm the occurrence of the square-law dependence of I_{TPEF} on the excitation power.

The δ_{TPA} values of samples (X) were determined through the equation:

$$\delta_{TPA,X} = \frac{k_{ref} \delta_{ref} \Phi_{ref} n_{ref} C_{ref} P_{ref}^2}{k_X \Phi_X n_X C_X P_X^2} \frac{I_X}{I_{ref}}$$

where k is the fluorescence collection efficiency, Φ is the two-photon fluorescence quantum yield, n the refractive index, C the concentration of the solutions, P the incident power and I is the intensity of two-photon excited fluorescence. Rhodamine 6G, having a well-known TPA spectrum was used as reference.^[20] Finally, for the calculation of δ_{TPA} , the fluorescence quantum yield upon two-photon excitation was assumed to be the same as that upon one-photon excitation, following the analysis of Xu et al.^[18]

Figure S7. TPA action cross-sections ($\delta_{\text{TPA}} \Phi_f$) of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene

Figure S8. TPA cross-sections (δ_{TPA}) of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene

Figure S9. Overlap of one-photon (OPA) and two-photon (TPA) absorption spectra of **bisbtz** in toluene, confirming the quadrupolar nature of dyes with a deeper $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition as compared to OPA ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$) process.

Figure S10. Plot of $\log(I_{TPEF})$ vs. $\log(\text{laser power})$ for selected **bisbtz** dye solutions. The slopes in all cases were exactly 2.00 ($R^2 > 0.99$) confirming the quadratic law dependence and assuring that emission is due to a two-photon induced process.

Figure S11. Comparison of TPA cross-sections for **bpy**, pertinent *push-pull* 2-H-benzothiazoles (**btz-IV**, **btz-VI**) and quadrupolar systems thereof (**bisbtz-IV**, **bisbtz-VI**) in toluene, demonstrating remarkable TPA enhancement in the latter series.

Figure S12. TPA cross-sections of **bisbtz-IV** and **bisbtz-VI** in toluene and chloroform

11 X-ray structure analysis

Crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction studies were obtained by dissolving **bisbtz-I** in chloroform, layering it with *n*-hexane and by slow evaporation of solvents.

Single-crystal diffraction data for **bisbtz-I** were collected on a Bruker D8 VENTURE Kappa Duo diffractometer equipped with a PHOTON 100 CMOS detector and using monochromatic Cu- $K\alpha$ primary radiation. The phase problem was solved by intrinsic phasing (SHELXT)^[21] and the structure model was refined by full-matrix least-squares on F^2 values (SHELXL).^[22] All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically and with no restraints applied. Hydrogen atoms were put into idealized positions and were refined isotropically. Difference Fourier maps suggested the presence of some additional solvent molecule(s) in the crystal lattice, but since this solvent could not be modelled with satisfactory results, its contribution was subtracted from the data by using the SQUEEZE procedure in PLATON.^[23]

CCDC 2056840 contains deposited data for the structure reported in this paper. Copies of data can be obtained free of charge from CCDC, e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

Figure S13. Molecular structure of **bisbtz-I**

Table S2. Crystal data and structure refinement for **bisbtz-I**

CCDC No.	2056840
Empirical formula	C ₃₈ H ₂₆ N ₄ S ₂
Formula weight	602.75
Temperature	125(2) K
Wavelength	1.54178 Å
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, P2(1)/c
Unit cell dimensions	a = 7.8308(6) Å alpha = 90 deg. b = 22.3973(18) Å beta = 93.874(3) deg. c = 10.0013(8) Å gamma = 90 deg.
Volume	1750.1(2) Å ³
Z, Calculated density	2, 1.144 g/cm ³
Absorption coefficient	1.607 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	628
Crystal size	0.268 × 0.262 × 0.127 mm
Theta range for data collection	3.947 to 72.448 deg.
Limiting indices	-9<=h<=9, -27<=k<=27, -12<=l<=11
Reflections collected / unique	36144 / 3458 [R(int) = 0.0319]
Completeness to theta = 67.679	100.0 %
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents
Max. and min. transmission	0.82 and 0.69
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Data / restraints / parameters	3458 / 0 / 199
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.089
Final R indices [I > 2sigma(I)]	R1 = 0.0348, wR2 = 0.0976
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0362, wR2 = 0.0992
Extinction coefficient	n/a
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.425 and -0.140 e. Å ⁻³

Table S3. Atomic coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **bisbtz-I**. $U(\text{eq})$ is defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalized U_{ij} tensor.

	x	y	z	U(eq)
C(1)	533(2)	4744(1)	4856(1)	31(1)
S(1)	-428(1)	4083(1)	4256(1)	33(1)
N(1)	2189(1)	4748(1)	5032(1)	33(1)
C(2)	2835(2)	4196(1)	4694(1)	31(1)
C(3)	1602(2)	3771(1)	4250(1)	29(1)
C(4)	2045(2)	3197(1)	3862(1)	31(1)
C(5)	3775(2)	3047(1)	3948(1)	31(1)
C(6)	5011(2)	3464(1)	4434(1)	35(1)
C(7)	4569(2)	4035(1)	4783(2)	34(1)
N(2)	4288(1)	2474(1)	3535(1)	35(1)
C(8)	3289(2)	1965(1)	3822(1)	33(1)
C(9)	2608(2)	1899(1)	5071(1)	35(1)
C(10)	1684(2)	1394(1)	5352(1)	39(1)
C(11)	1439(2)	941(1)	4413(2)	43(1)
C(12)	2106(2)	1005(1)	3170(2)	42(1)
C(13)	2996(2)	1515(1)	2865(1)	37(1)
C(14)	5819(2)	2406(1)	2859(1)	34(1)
C(15)	6795(2)	1889(1)	3035(2)	40(1)
C(16)	8288(2)	1822(1)	2374(2)	48(1)
C(17)	8837(2)	2266(1)	1557(2)	47(1)
C(18)	7874(2)	2780(1)	1379(2)	45(1)
C(19)	6366(2)	2850(1)	2014(1)	39(1)

Table S4. Bond lengths [$\text{\AA}$] and angles [deg] for **bisbtz-I**

C(1)-N(1)	1.2974(17)
C(1)-C(1)#1	1.456(2)
C(1)-S(1)	1.7489(13)
S(1)-C(3)	1.7368(12)
N(1)-C(2)	1.3853(16)
C(2)-C(7)	1.4021(18)
C(2)-C(3)	1.4066(18)
C(3)-C(4)	1.3940(17)
C(4)-C(5)	1.3926(18)
C(4)-H(4)	0.9500
C(5)-C(6)	1.4089(19)
C(5)-N(2)	1.4147(16)
C(6)-C(7)	1.3747(18)
C(6)-H(6)	0.9500
C(7)-H(7)	0.9500
N(2)-C(8)	1.4235(17)

N(2)-C(14)	1.4243(16)
C(8)-C(13)	1.3975(19)
C(8)-C(9)	1.3981(19)
C(9)-C(10)	1.381(2)
C(9)-H(9)	0.9500
C(10)-C(11)	1.388(2)
C(10)-H(10)	0.9500
C(11)-C(12)	1.388(2)
C(11)-H(11)	0.9500
C(12)-C(13)	1.384(2)
C(12)-H(12)	0.9500
C(13)-H(13)	0.9500
C(14)-C(15)	1.3915(19)
C(14)-C(19)	1.392(2)
C(15)-C(16)	1.389(2)
C(15)-H(15)	0.9500
C(16)-C(17)	1.374(2)
C(16)-H(16)	0.9500
C(17)-C(18)	1.381(2)
C(17)-H(17)	0.9500
C(18)-C(19)	1.387(2)
C(18)-H(18)	0.9500
C(19)-H(19)	0.9500

N(1)-C(1)-C(1)#1	123.37(15)
N(1)-C(1)-S(1)	117.00(9)
C(1)#1-C(1)-S(1)	119.63(13)
C(3)-S(1)-C(1)	88.26(6)
C(1)-N(1)-C(2)	109.90(11)
N(1)-C(2)-C(7)	125.63(12)
N(1)-C(2)-C(3)	115.22(11)
C(7)-C(2)-C(3)	119.14(11)
C(4)-C(3)-C(2)	122.25(11)
C(4)-C(3)-S(1)	128.13(10)
C(2)-C(3)-S(1)	109.61(9)
C(5)-C(4)-C(3)	117.71(12)
C(5)-C(4)-H(4)	121.1
C(3)-C(4)-H(4)	121.1
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	120.27(12)
C(4)-C(5)-N(2)	119.67(12)
C(6)-C(5)-N(2)	120.06(11)
C(7)-C(6)-C(5)	121.69(12)
C(7)-C(6)-H(6)	119.2
C(5)-C(6)-H(6)	119.2
C(6)-C(7)-C(2)	118.88(12)
C(6)-C(7)-H(7)	120.6
C(2)-C(7)-H(7)	120.6
C(5)-N(2)-C(8)	119.80(10)
C(5)-N(2)-C(14)	120.07(11)
C(8)-N(2)-C(14)	120.12(11)
C(13)-C(8)-C(9)	118.78(12)

C(13)-C(8)-N(2)	120.36(12)
C(9)-C(8)-N(2)	120.85(12)
C(10)-C(9)-C(8)	120.33(13)
C(10)-C(9)-H(9)	119.8
C(8)-C(9)-H(9)	119.8
C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	120.72(13)
C(9)-C(10)-H(10)	119.6
C(11)-C(10)-H(10)	119.6
C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	119.20(13)
C(10)-C(11)-H(11)	120.4
C(12)-C(11)-H(11)	120.4
C(13)-C(12)-C(11)	120.57(13)
C(13)-C(12)-H(12)	119.7
C(11)-C(12)-H(12)	119.7
C(12)-C(13)-C(8)	120.35(13)
C(12)-C(13)-H(13)	119.8
C(8)-C(13)-H(13)	119.8
C(15)-C(14)-C(19)	118.90(13)
C(15)-C(14)-N(2)	120.14(13)
C(19)-C(14)-N(2)	120.96(12)
C(16)-C(15)-C(14)	120.08(15)
C(16)-C(15)-H(15)	120.0
C(14)-C(15)-H(15)	120.0
C(17)-C(16)-C(15)	120.85(15)
C(17)-C(16)-H(16)	119.6
C(15)-C(16)-H(16)	119.6
C(16)-C(17)-C(18)	119.32(13)
C(16)-C(17)-H(17)	120.3
C(18)-C(17)-H(17)	120.3
C(17)-C(18)-C(19)	120.65(15)
C(17)-C(18)-H(18)	119.7
C(19)-C(18)-H(18)	119.7
C(18)-C(19)-C(14)	120.19(14)
C(18)-C(19)-H(19)	119.9
C(14)-C(19)-H(19)	119.9

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms:
 #1 -x, -y+1, -z+1

Table S5. Anisotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **bisbtz-I**. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2 [h^2 a^{*2} U_{11} + \dots + 2hk a^* b^* U_{12}]$

	U11	U22	U33	U23	U13	U12
C(1)	32(1)	25(1)	37(1)	5(1)	7(1)	2(1)
S(1)	25(1)	26(1)	48(1)	0(1)	6(1)	3(1)
N(1)	31(1)	25(1)	42(1)	2(1)	7(1)	2(1)
C(2)	30(1)	25(1)	37(1)	3(1)	7(1)	1(1)
C(3)	26(1)	28(1)	35(1)	4(1)	6(1)	2(1)
C(4)	28(1)	27(1)	38(1)	0(1)	6(1)	0(1)
C(5)	31(1)	26(1)	38(1)	0(1)	8(1)	4(1)
C(6)	26(1)	33(1)	46(1)	0(1)	6(1)	3(1)
C(7)	28(1)	29(1)	46(1)	-1(1)	4(1)	-1(1)
N(2)	31(1)	28(1)	47(1)	-4(1)	12(1)	3(1)
C(8)	29(1)	27(1)	42(1)	-1(1)	6(1)	6(1)
C(9)	35(1)	31(1)	40(1)	-2(1)	4(1)	6(1)
C(10)	40(1)	38(1)	40(1)	3(1)	9(1)	4(1)
C(11)	43(1)	31(1)	55(1)	3(1)	6(1)	-1(1)
C(12)	42(1)	34(1)	50(1)	-7(1)	2(1)	2(1)
C(13)	36(1)	35(1)	40(1)	-3(1)	7(1)	4(1)
C(14)	28(1)	38(1)	37(1)	-5(1)	6(1)	3(1)
C(15)	35(1)	40(1)	45(1)	-3(1)	6(1)	7(1)
C(16)	36(1)	53(1)	54(1)	-12(1)	5(1)	14(1)
C(17)	31(1)	63(1)	50(1)	-15(1)	11(1)	0(1)
C(18)	38(1)	57(1)	42(1)	-3(1)	8(1)	-9(1)
C(19)	33(1)	41(1)	43(1)	0(1)	5(1)	1(1)

Table S6. Hydrogen coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **bisbtz-I**

	x	y	z	U(eq)
H(4)	1196	2918	3549	37
H(6)	6181	3349	4523	42
H(7)	5424	4315	5079	41
H(9)	2781	2203	5728	42
H(10)	1211	1357	6199	47
H(11)	822	591	4618	52
H(12)	1950	695	2524	51
H(13)	3411	1560	2000	44
H(15)	6440	1581	3608	48
H(16)	8937	1465	2488	57
H(17)	9869	2220	1120	57
H(18)	8248	3088	816	55
H(19)	5705	3203	1873	47

Table S7. Torsion angles [deg] for **bisbtz-I**

N(1)-C(1)-S(1)-C(3)	0.57(11)
C(1)#1-C(1)-S(1)-C(3)	-178.92(14)
C(1)#1-C(1)-N(1)-C(2)	178.96(15)
S(1)-C(1)-N(1)-C(2)	-0.51(14)
C(1)-N(1)-C(2)-C(7)	-178.75(13)
C(1)-N(1)-C(2)-C(3)	0.14(16)
N(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	179.40(11)
C(7)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	-1.63(19)
N(1)-C(2)-C(3)-S(1)	0.27(14)
C(7)-C(2)-C(3)-S(1)	179.24(10)
C(1)-S(1)-C(3)-C(4)	-179.50(12)
C(1)-S(1)-C(3)-C(2)	-0.43(10)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	1.17(19)
S(1)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	-179.88(10)
C(3)-C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	0.96(19)
C(3)-C(4)-C(5)-N(2)	-178.51(11)
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)-C(7)	-2.7(2)
N(2)-C(5)-C(6)-C(7)	176.77(13)
C(5)-C(6)-C(7)-C(2)	2.2(2)
N(1)-C(2)-C(7)-C(6)	178.77(13)
C(3)-C(2)-C(7)-C(6)	-0.1(2)
C(4)-C(5)-N(2)-C(8)	-39.05(18)
C(6)-C(5)-N(2)-C(8)	141.47(13)
C(4)-C(5)-N(2)-C(14)	142.32(13)
C(6)-C(5)-N(2)-C(14)	-37.15(19)
C(5)-N(2)-C(8)-C(13)	139.09(13)
C(14)-N(2)-C(8)-C(13)	-42.29(19)
C(5)-N(2)-C(8)-C(9)	-42.03(18)
C(14)-N(2)-C(8)-C(9)	136.60(13)
C(13)-C(8)-C(9)-C(10)	0.9(2)
N(2)-C(8)-C(9)-C(10)	-178.03(12)
C(8)-C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	1.0(2)
C(9)-C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	-1.3(2)
C(10)-C(11)-C(12)-C(13)	-0.4(2)
C(11)-C(12)-C(13)-C(8)	2.3(2)
C(9)-C(8)-C(13)-C(12)	-2.5(2)
N(2)-C(8)-C(13)-C(12)	176.40(12)
C(5)-N(2)-C(14)-C(15)	147.35(13)
C(8)-N(2)-C(14)-C(15)	-31.26(19)
C(5)-N(2)-C(14)-C(19)	-32.68(19)
C(8)-N(2)-C(14)-C(19)	148.70(13)
C(19)-C(14)-C(15)-C(16)	0.0(2)
N(2)-C(14)-C(15)-C(16)	179.93(13)
C(14)-C(15)-C(16)-C(17)	1.0(2)
C(15)-C(16)-C(17)-C(18)	-1.0(2)
C(16)-C(17)-C(18)-C(19)	0.0(2)
C(17)-C(18)-C(19)-C(14)	1.0(2)
C(15)-C(14)-C(19)-C(18)	-1.0(2)
N(2)-C(14)-C(19)-C(18)	179.07(13)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms:

#1 -x, -y+1, -z+1

12 Computational details and results

The ground-state structures of all systems under investigation were fully optimized at the PBE0^{[24],[25]} level of theory, employing all-electron def2-TZVP basis set^[26] an atom-pairwise correction for dispersion forces via Grimme's D3 model^[27] with Becke-Johnson (BJ)^[28] damping, in the Turbomole program.^[29] All structures were characterized as true minima on the harmonic potential energy hypersurface through vibrational analysis (no imaginary frequencies were found).

The two-component relativistic all-electron DFT calculations of the NMR nuclear shieldings^{[30],[31]} were performed using the Amsterdam Density Functional (ADF)^[32] program suite,^[33] employing the global hybrid PBE0 (with 25% exact-exchange admixture)^[25] exchange-correlation functional, in conjunction with Slater-type orbital basis sets of triple- ζ doubly polarized (TZ2P) quality and an integration accuracy of 5.0. The relativistic zeroth-order regular approximation (ZORA)^{[30],[31],[33]} calculations of NMR shieldings were done by using gauge-including atomic orbitals (GIAOs).^[34] The computed ¹⁵N and ¹H nuclear shieldings were converted to chemical shifts (δ , in ppm) relative to the shielding of nitromethane and tetramethylsilane (TMS), respectively.

Time-dependent DFT method using the Coulomb-attenuated CAM-B3LYP^[35] exchange-correlation functional, respectively, in conjunction with the 6-311++G** basis set was applied to get vertical excitation energies (E_n), transition dipole moments (μ_{0n}) and adiabatic dipole moment changes ($\Delta\mu_{0n}$) between the ground-state and the n -th excited state. The excited-to-excited transition dipole moments μ_{1n} were obtained from the double-residue of the quadratic response function. All these calculations were carried out with the Dalton program.^[36]

The TPA cross-sections δ_{TPA} were evaluated by calculating the two-photon transition moment matrix elements $S_{\alpha\beta}$ in the Dalton program. The matrix elements $S_{\alpha\beta}$ for the two-photon resonant absorption of identical energy can be identified from the sum-over-states formula a

$$S_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_n \left[\frac{\langle 0|\mu_\alpha|n\rangle\langle n|\mu_\beta|f\rangle}{\omega_n - \frac{\omega_f}{2}} + \frac{\langle 0|\mu_\beta|n\rangle\langle n|\mu_\alpha|f\rangle}{\omega_n - \frac{\omega_f}{2}} \right] \quad (\alpha, \beta = x, y, z) \quad (Eq. S1)$$

where ω_n represents the excitation energy from the ground state $|0\rangle$ to the excited state $|n\rangle$, $\omega_f/2$ corresponds to half of the excitation energy associated with the transition from the ground to the final excited state $|f\rangle$, μ_α and μ_β are the Cartesian components of the electronic dipole moment operator. The explicit summation over all excited states of the molecule was avoided through the use of quadratic response theory. Within this formalism, matrix elements $S_{\alpha\beta}$ are extracted as a single residue of the appropriate quadratic response function for the dipole moment operators. This approach is described in detail in refs. [37], [38] and [39].

TPA cross-sections of molecules for linearly polarized monochromatic light were calculated (in atomic units) from $S_{\alpha\beta}$ elements as:

$$\delta_{a.u.} = \frac{1}{30} \sum_{\alpha,\beta} (2S_{\alpha\alpha}S_{\beta\beta}^* + 4S_{\alpha\beta}S_{\beta\alpha}^*) \quad (Eq. S2)$$

Finally, $\delta_{a.u.}$ values were converted to TPA cross-sections δ_{TPA} , which are directly comparable to experiment, using the following relationship:

$$\delta_{TPA} = \frac{(2\pi)^3 \alpha a_0^5 \omega^2}{c \pi \Gamma} \delta_{a.u.} \quad (Eq. S3)$$

Here, α is the fine structure constant, a_0 the Bohr radius, c the speed of light, ω the energy of the exciting photon (in case of the TPA process, one half of the excitation energy) and $\pi\Gamma$ a normalization factor due to the Lorentzian line-shape broadening of the excited state ($\Gamma = 0.2$ eV was used throughout this work). The units of δ_{TPA} will become GM ($\text{cm}^4 \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{photon}^{-1}$), provided we use centimeter-gram-second units for a_0 and c , and atomic units for ω and Γ . Note that effects on nuclear motion, which may also contribute to δ_{TPA} , are not included in our treatment.

Table S8. Calculated one-photon absorption parameters and TPA cross-sections for the first 3 excitations at the CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory (*in vacuo*) for pertinent *push-pull* 2-H-benzothiazole (**btz-VI**), quadrupolar 2,2'-bibenzothiazole (**bisbtz-VI**) and its 2,2'-bipyridine-cored congener (see Computational details).^a

System	n	E _n [eV]	μ _{0n} [D]	Δμ _{0n} [D]	μ _{1n} [D]	δ _{TPA} [GM]	δ _{TPA} ^{expt,b} [GM]
 btz-VI	1	3.49	10.2	9.4		65	64 ^c
	2	4.05	1.9	1.0	1.0	2	
	3	4.33	3.5	1.2	0.8	18	
 bisbtz-VI	1	3.04	17.8	0.2		0	1252 ^c
	2	3.44	0.1	0.2	13.4	1320	
	3	3.89	2.3	0.2	0.1	1	
 bpy	1	3.43	14.4	0.4		0	210 ^{c,d}
	2	3.56	0.3	0.4	9.9	340	
	3	4.08	1.8	0.1	0.3	9	

^a Only *s-trans* configuration considered in calculations of biheteroaryls. Since *s-cis* conformers are energetically disfavored by ca. 24 kJ/mol, they give rise to a negligible Boltzmann weighting factor.

^b Experimental TPA cross-sections at their resonant maxima. ^c This work (see Figure S11 in SI). ^d In ref. [40], the maximum TPA cross-section for **bpy** in chloroform is reported as high as 219 GM at 690 nm.

Table S9. Calculated one-photon absorption parameters and TPA cross-sections for the first three excitations at the CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory (see Computational details).^a

System	n	E _n [eV]	μ _{0n} [D]	Δμ _{0n} [D]	μ _{1n} [D]	δ _{TPA} [GM]
<p>bisbtz-I</p>	1	3.24	11.2	0.0		0
	2	3.77	0.3	0.0	14.0	730
	3	4.08	1.1	0.1	1.8	22
<p>bisbtz-II</p>	1	3.40	13.8	0.1		0
	2	3.80	0.0	0.1	16.6	1020
	3	4.09	0.4	0.0	0.1	0
<p>bisbtz-III</p>	1	3.29	13.9	0.1		0
	2	3.64	0.0	0.2	20.9	1400
	3	3.85	1.0	0.0	0.1	2
<p>bisbtz-IV</p>	1	3.15	17.2	0.4		0
	2	3.56	0.3	0.5	16.1	1680
	3	4.10	3.0	0.3	0.1	0
<p>bisbtz-V</p>	1	3.10	17.3	0.1		0
	2	3.48	0.1	0.2	20.7	2550
	3	4.01	2.3	0.1	0.0	0
<p>bisbtz-VI</p>	1	3.04	17.8	0.2		0
	2	3.44	0.1	0.2	13.4	1320
	3	3.89	2.3	0.2	0.1	1

^a Only *s-trans* configuration considered in the calculations. Since *s-cis* conformers are energetically disfavored by ca. 24 kJ/mol, they give rise to a negligible Boltzmann weighting factor.

Considering only the first ($n = 1$) or first two ($n = 1, 2$) excited states in the summation of Eq. S1 above and taking Eqs. S2 and S3 into account, one can derive the following two- and three-state models for TPA cross-sections:

Two-state model for dipoles

$$\delta_{TPA}^{2SM}(S_0 \rightarrow S_1) = \frac{8\pi^2 \alpha a_0^5}{15c} \frac{1}{\Gamma} \left(\underbrace{4|\mu_{01}|^2 |\Delta\mu_{01}|^2 (1 + 2\cos^2\varphi)}_{\text{two-state "dipolar" term}} \right)$$

Three-state model for (*quasi*-)quadrupoles

$$\delta_{TPA}^{3SM}(S_0 \rightarrow S_2) = \frac{8\pi^2 \alpha a_0^5}{15c} \frac{1}{\Gamma} \left(\underbrace{E_2^2 \frac{|\mu_{01}|^2 |\mu_{12}|^2}{\left(E_1 - \frac{E_2}{2}\right)^2} (1 + 2\cos^2\theta)}_{\text{three-state term}} + \underbrace{4|\mu_{02}|^2 |\Delta\mu_{02}|^2 (1 + 2\cos^2\varphi)}_{\text{two-state "dipolar" term}} \right)$$

In true quadrupoles the dipolar terms diminish due to $\Delta\mu_{0n} = 0$. φ is the angle between the vectors μ_{0n} and $\Delta\mu_{0n}$, and θ is the angle between the vectors μ_{01} and μ_{12} . In all systems under investigation, the corresponding vectors are oriented almost parallel or anti-parallel with respect to each other, giving constant factors $(1 + 2\cos^2\theta) \approx 3$ and $(1 + 2\cos^2\varphi) \approx 3$.

Table S10. Analysis of TPA cross-sections in pertinent systems relevant to this work

System	$ \mu_{01} $	$ \Delta\mu_{01} $	$ \mu_{12} $	$E_1 - E_2/2$	δ_{TPA}^{SM}	δ_{TPA}^{full}
	[D]	[D]	[D]	[eV]	[GM]	[GM]
btz-VI	10.2	9.4	1.0	1.47	189	65
bisbtz-VI	17.8	0.2	13.4	1.32	2010	1320
bpy	14.4	0.4	9.9	1.65	494	340

TPA cross-sections estimated from the two- or three-state model follow the trends obtained from response theory (δ_{TPA}^{full}), justifying the use of these simplified models for more detailed analysis. Hence, the TPA superiority of **bisbtz-VI** can be ascribed to the highest transition dipole moments μ_{01} and μ_{12} and the reduced detuning energy ($E_1 - E_2/2$).

Table S11. Comparison of calculated and experimental key NMR resonances in **bisbtz-I** and its rhenium complex (^{15}N NMR shifts wrt. to CH_3NO_2 , ^1H NMR shifts wrt. to TMS). Chemical shieldings are decomposed into diamagnetic, paramagnetic and spin-orbit contributions.

	σ^{dia}	σ^{p}	σ^{SO}	δ_{calcd}	δ_{expt}
N_{bbtz}	317.0	-389.2	1.2	-69.0	-69.8
N_{NPh_2}	305.8	-170.4	0.0	-275.4	-279.3
H-4_{bbtz}	31.44	-8.11	0.0	7.97	7.93
H-5_{bbtz}	30.79	-6.88	0.0	7.39	7.30
H-7_{bbtz}	30.64	-7.08	0.0	7.74	7.53
	σ^{dia}	σ^{p}	σ^{SO}	δ_{calcd}	δ_{expt}
N_{bbtz}	313.2	-342.8	10.4	-120.8	-123.7
N_{NPh_2}	306.1	-174.6	1.2	-272.7	-274.6
H-4_{bbtz}	30.63	-7.94	0.0	8.61	8.31
H-5_{bbtz}	30.65	-7.02	0.0	7.67	7.45
H-7_{bbtz}	30.52	-6.94	0.0	7.72	7.42

^a Calculations done at the 2c-ZORA(SO)/TZ2P level (cf. Computational details).

13 Cartesian coordinates of pertinent DFT optimized structures

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bisbtz-I

C	0.7149608	0.0939836	-0.0035178
S	1.7788130	-1.2900368	0.0047899
C	3.1202689	-0.2049355	0.0003900
C	2.6477823	1.1241957	-0.0076484
N	1.2877067	1.2552757	-0.0076871
C	3.5723614	2.1709972	-0.0122061
C	4.9160038	1.8835278	-0.0011204
C	5.3809385	0.5543991	-0.0013392
C	4.4751779	-0.4993008	-0.0082807
H	3.2177938	3.1942522	-0.0060335
H	5.6423630	2.6861460	0.0125970
H	4.8317958	-1.5211798	-0.0124509
C	-0.7149608	-0.0939836	-0.0035178
S	-1.7788130	1.2900368	0.0047899
C	-3.1202689	0.2049355	0.0003900
C	-2.6477823	-1.1241957	-0.0076484
N	-1.2877067	-1.2552757	-0.0076871
C	-3.5723614	-2.1709972	-0.0122061
C	-4.9160038	-1.8835278	-0.0011204
C	-5.3809385	-0.5543991	-0.0013392
C	-4.4751779	0.4993008	-0.0082807
H	-3.2177938	-3.1942522	-0.0060335
H	-5.6423630	-2.6861460	0.0125970
H	-4.8317958	1.5211798	-0.0124509
N	-6.7598912	-0.3006302	0.0184215
C	-7.2664851	0.7816738	0.7632746
C	-8.2628099	1.5988900	0.2341137
C	-8.7624790	2.6566533	0.9749530
C	-8.2685048	2.9250280	2.2430138
C	-7.2714509	2.1153673	2.7685222
C	-6.7773851	1.0466476	2.0412212
C	-7.6350791	-1.0950400	-0.7446057
C	-8.8804394	-1.4587231	-0.2343633
C	-9.7418812	-2.2359670	-0.9888268
C	-9.3733935	-2.6751484	-2.2527384
C	-8.1319845	-2.3190817	-2.7590677
C	-7.2701614	-1.5282485	-2.0180384
H	-8.6434558	1.3959792	-0.7595203
H	-9.5364057	3.2848696	0.5490220
H	-8.6569702	3.7574724	2.8170269
H	-6.8817035	2.3083165	3.7614372
H	-6.0060909	0.4095055	2.4568051
H	-9.1662455	-1.1253237	0.7557494
H	-10.7060988	-2.5122172	-0.5777633
H	-10.0478857	-3.2887830	-2.8374240
H	-7.8334590	-2.6475659	-3.7479683
H	-6.3062965	-1.2416542	-2.4206818
N	6.7598912	0.3006302	0.0184215
C	7.2664851	-0.7816738	0.7632746
C	8.2628099	-1.5988900	0.2341137
C	8.7624790	-2.6566533	0.9749530
C	8.2685048	-2.9250280	2.2430138

C	7.2714509	-2.1153673	2.7685222
C	6.7773851	-1.0466476	2.0412212
C	7.6350791	1.0950400	-0.7446057
C	8.8804394	1.4587231	-0.2343633
C	9.7418812	2.2359670	-0.9888268
C	9.3733935	2.6751484	-2.2527384
C	8.1319845	2.3190817	-2.7590677
C	7.2701614	1.5282485	-2.0180384
H	8.6434558	-1.3959792	-0.7595203
H	9.5364057	-3.2848696	0.5490220
H	8.6569702	-3.7574724	2.8170269
H	6.8817035	-2.3083165	3.7614372
H	6.0060909	-0.4095055	2.4568051
H	9.1662455	1.1253237	0.7557494
H	10.7060988	2.5122172	-0.5777633
H	10.0478857	3.2887830	-2.8374240
H	7.8334590	2.6475659	-3.7479683
H	6.3062965	1.2416542	-2.4206818

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bisbtz-II

C	0.7161362	0.0924685	-0.0378730
S	1.7756157	-1.2916444	-0.0398569
C	3.1187526	-0.2084304	-0.0403530
C	2.6490493	1.1213258	-0.0340022
N	1.2880757	1.2538806	-0.0353936
C	3.5720215	2.1682977	-0.0242289
C	4.9152920	1.8743046	-0.0196408
C	5.3896640	0.5477566	-0.0240201
C	4.4752128	-0.4992620	-0.0333510
H	3.2163536	3.1911140	-0.0306018
H	5.6353207	2.6833980	-0.0413186
H	4.8221650	-1.5248698	-0.0056854
C	-0.7161362	-0.0924685	-0.0378730
S	-1.7756157	1.2916444	-0.0398569
C	-3.1187526	0.2084304	-0.0403530
C	-2.6490493	-1.1213258	-0.0340022
N	-1.2880757	-1.2538806	-0.0353936
C	-3.5720215	-2.1682977	-0.0242289
C	-4.9152920	-1.8743046	-0.0196408
C	-5.3896640	-0.5477566	-0.0240201
C	-4.4752128	0.4992620	-0.0333510
H	-3.2163536	-3.1911140	-0.0306018
H	-5.6353207	-2.6833980	-0.0413186
H	-4.8221650	1.5248698	-0.0056854
C	-6.8345422	-0.2764491	-0.0192013
C	6.8345422	0.2764491	-0.0192013
C	-7.3718598	0.8069440	-0.7159496
C	-8.7286965	1.0628003	-0.7172319
C	-9.6046889	0.2455924	-0.0024709
C	-9.0781271	-0.8362776	0.7031242
C	-7.7214386	-1.0924267	0.6846588
H	-6.7176884	1.4388273	-1.3059836
H	-9.1230884	1.8970517	-1.2842952
N	-10.9819407	0.5039062	0.0050900
H	-9.7424711	-1.4721679	1.2751065
H	-7.3363181	-1.9222154	1.2664662

C	-11.4547724	1.8291661	0.0255446
C	-12.5549200	2.1956049	-0.7473777
C	-13.0263225	3.4968080	-0.7165490
C	-12.4027049	4.4545643	0.0700471
C	-11.3028680	4.0928500	0.8345239
C	-10.8342718	2.7902519	0.8215797
C	-11.9005584	-0.5625418	-0.0006718
C	-13.0390384	-0.5162102	0.8014675
C	-13.9448144	-1.5629911	0.7868732
C	-13.7246382	-2.6750547	-0.0128521
C	-12.5885649	-2.7249320	-0.8077243
C	-11.6853536	-1.6759666	-0.8104803
H	-13.0376970	1.4512383	-1.3689040
H	-13.8823367	3.7663418	-1.3245811
H	-12.7708299	5.4731521	0.0877687
H	-10.8110670	4.8282517	1.4609509
H	-9.9825937	2.5076264	1.4283640
H	-13.2081838	0.3476786	1.4328109
H	-14.8247529	-1.5134759	1.4180627
H	-14.4322738	-3.4951587	-0.0173634
H	-12.4082043	-3.5832927	-1.4447496
H	-10.8042726	-1.7115480	-1.4397276
C	7.3718598	-0.8069440	-0.7159496
C	8.7286965	-1.0628003	-0.7172319
C	9.6046889	-0.2455924	-0.0024709
C	9.0781271	0.8362776	0.7031242
C	7.7214386	1.0924267	0.6846588
H	6.7176884	-1.4388273	-1.3059836
H	9.1230884	-1.8970517	-1.2842952
N	10.9819407	-0.5039062	0.0050900
H	9.7424711	1.4721679	1.2751065
H	7.3363181	1.9222154	1.2664662
C	11.4547724	-1.8291661	0.0255446
C	12.5549200	-2.1956049	-0.7473777
C	13.0263225	-3.4968080	-0.7165490
C	12.4027049	-4.4545643	0.0700471
C	11.3028680	-4.0928500	0.8345239
C	10.8342718	-2.7902519	0.8215797
C	11.9005584	0.5625418	-0.0006718
C	13.0390384	0.5162102	0.8014675
C	13.9448144	1.5629911	0.7868732
C	13.7246382	2.6750547	-0.0128521
C	12.5885649	2.7249320	-0.8077243
C	11.6853536	1.6759666	-0.8104803
H	13.0376970	-1.4512383	-1.3689040
H	13.8823367	-3.7663418	-1.3245811
H	12.7708299	-5.4731521	0.0877687
H	10.8110670	-4.8282517	1.4609509
H	9.9825937	-2.5076264	1.4283640
H	13.2081838	-0.3476786	1.4328109
H	14.8247529	1.5134759	1.4180627
H	14.4322738	3.4951587	-0.0173634
H	12.4082043	3.5832927	-1.4447496
H	10.8042726	1.7115480	-1.4397276

bisbtz-III

C	0.7156514	0.0942899	-0.0656900
S	1.7786418	-1.2874279	-0.0643309
C	3.1194365	-0.2011203	-0.0641111
C	2.6464515	1.1274418	-0.0594704
N	1.2852479	1.2569398	-0.0627409
C	3.5676519	2.1760373	-0.0482882
C	4.9114415	1.8847424	-0.0417420
C	5.3895731	0.5592085	-0.0442161
C	4.4762136	-0.4891913	-0.0548206
H	3.2100650	3.1982239	-0.0559083
H	5.6296919	2.6954257	-0.0629295
H	4.8247899	-1.5141538	-0.0250995
C	-0.7156514	-0.0942899	-0.0656900
S	-1.7786418	1.2874279	-0.0643309
C	-3.1194365	0.2011203	-0.0641111
C	-2.6464515	-1.1274418	-0.0594704
N	-1.2852479	-1.2569398	-0.0627409
C	-3.5676519	-2.1760373	-0.0482882
C	-4.9114415	-1.8847424	-0.0417420
C	-5.3895731	-0.5592085	-0.0442161
C	-4.4762136	0.4891913	-0.0548206
H	-3.2100650	-3.1982239	-0.0559083
H	-5.6296919	-2.6954257	-0.0629295
H	-4.8247899	1.5141538	-0.0250995
C	-6.8339035	-0.2904230	-0.0366078
C	6.8339035	0.2904230	-0.0366078
C	-7.3744193	0.7993261	-0.7212397
C	-8.7305145	1.0557373	-0.7182420
C	-9.6093133	0.2317603	-0.0107922
C	-9.0776930	-0.8580622	0.6826089
C	-7.7212647	-1.1124341	0.6598729
H	-6.7220824	1.4372084	-1.3070627
H	-9.1239252	1.8958413	-1.2770002
N	-10.9807369	0.4894701	0.0019248
H	-9.7394524	-1.5008874	1.2495232
H	-7.3359798	-1.9475403	1.2341496
C	-11.4625574	1.8134797	-0.0436842
C	-12.5447230	2.1444798	-0.8600167
C	-13.0322481	3.4333131	-0.8961787
C	-12.4387714	4.4345549	-0.1300403
C	-11.3554582	4.1168216	0.6812366
C	-10.8851175	2.8120841	0.7284462
C	-11.9076796	-0.5706072	0.0686544
C	-13.0094528	-0.4950728	0.9211523
C	-13.9269612	-1.5219620	0.9791932
C	-13.7589348	-2.6641575	0.1990641
C	-12.6609490	-2.7519775	-0.6490270
C	-11.7541613	-1.7040881	-0.7173939
H	-13.0070959	1.3739858	-1.4653003
H	-13.8728975	3.6928068	-1.5282007
O	-12.9789945	5.6708354	-0.2400326
H	-10.8782458	4.8696153	1.2940588
H	-10.0483203	2.5685747	1.3720263
H	-13.1434269	0.3858336	1.5376226
H	-14.7838001	-1.4663083	1.6397419

O	-14.7036297	-3.6238952	0.3334583
H	-12.5068601	-3.6215539	-1.2736584
H	-10.9063601	-1.7732542	-1.3886908
C	7.3744193	-0.7993261	-0.7212397
C	8.7305145	-1.0557373	-0.7182420
C	9.6093133	-0.2317603	-0.0107922
C	9.0776930	0.8580622	0.6826089
C	7.7212647	1.1124341	0.6598729
H	6.7220824	-1.4372084	-1.3070627
H	9.1239252	-1.8958413	-1.2770002
N	10.9807369	-0.4894701	0.0019248
H	9.7394524	1.5008874	1.2495232
H	7.3359798	1.9475403	1.2341496
C	11.4625574	-1.8134797	-0.0436842
C	12.5447230	-2.1444798	-0.8600167
C	13.0322481	-3.4333131	-0.8961787
C	12.4387714	-4.4345549	-0.1300403
C	11.3554582	-4.1168216	0.6812366
C	10.8851175	-2.8120841	0.7284462
C	11.9076796	0.5706072	0.0686544
C	13.0094528	0.4950728	0.9211523
C	13.9269612	1.5219620	0.9791932
C	13.7589348	2.6641575	0.1990641
C	12.6609490	2.7519775	-0.6490270
C	11.7541613	1.7040881	-0.7173939
H	13.0070959	-1.3739858	-1.4653003
H	13.8728975	-3.6928068	-1.5282007
O	12.9789945	-5.6708354	-0.2400326
H	10.8782458	-4.8696153	1.2940588
H	10.0483203	-2.5685747	1.3720263
H	13.1434269	-0.3858336	1.5376226
H	14.7838001	1.4663083	1.6397419
O	14.7036297	3.6238952	0.3334583
H	12.5068601	3.6215539	-1.2736584
H	10.9063601	1.7732542	-1.3886908
C	-12.4078280	6.7024646	0.5243593
H	-12.9743723	7.6029508	0.2938184
H	-12.4819309	6.4959719	1.5979124
H	-11.3558799	6.8620971	0.2622640
C	-14.5647885	-4.7886885	-0.4405256
H	-15.4093999	-5.4266495	-0.1864878
H	-14.5926470	-4.5651160	-1.5128615
H	-13.6326590	-5.3163243	-0.2091461
C	12.4078280	-6.7024646	0.5243593
H	12.9743723	-7.6029508	0.2938184
H	12.4819309	-6.4959719	1.5979124
H	11.3558799	-6.8620971	0.2622640
C	14.5647885	4.7886885	-0.4405256
H	15.4093999	5.4266495	-0.1864878
H	14.5926470	4.5651160	-1.5128615
H	13.6326590	5.3163243	-0.2091461

bisbtz-IV

C	0.6236388	-0.3630285	-0.2463455
S	0.6200903	-2.1053726	-0.2422480
C	2.3452357	-2.0642110	-0.2287099
C	2.7834927	-0.7219378	-0.2299571
N	1.7854233	0.2102564	-0.2407443
C	4.1534868	-0.4477188	-0.2156251
C	5.0446213	-1.4921552	-0.1972469
C	4.6056083	-2.8353005	-0.1939313
C	3.2408598	-3.1207771	-0.2120728
H	4.4889086	0.5818490	-0.2170106
H	6.1099235	-1.3000021	-0.1837708
C	5.5529395	-3.8858443	-0.1655163
H	2.9057710	-4.1498469	-0.2087538
C	-0.6236388	0.3630285	-0.2463455
S	-0.6200903	2.1053726	-0.2422480
C	-2.3452357	2.0642110	-0.2287099
C	-2.7834927	0.7219378	-0.2299571
N	-1.7854233	-0.2102564	-0.2407443
C	-4.1534868	0.4477188	-0.2156251
C	-5.0446213	1.4921552	-0.1972469
C	-4.6056083	2.8353005	-0.1939313
C	-3.2408598	3.1207771	-0.2120728
H	-4.4889086	-0.5818490	-0.2170106
H	-6.1099235	1.3000021	-0.1837708
C	-5.5529395	3.8858443	-0.1655163
H	-2.9057710	4.1498469	-0.2087538
C	-6.3680901	4.7789443	-0.1327655
C	-7.3206224	5.8229991	-0.0865326
C	6.3680901	-4.7789443	-0.1327655
C	7.3206224	-5.8229991	-0.0865326
C	-6.9260356	7.1637173	-0.1679638
C	-7.8541996	8.1817005	-0.1210912
C	-9.2154135	7.8992128	0.0215040
C	-9.6153758	6.5628034	0.1058658
C	-8.6864001	5.5461772	0.0471929
H	-5.8748986	7.3980235	-0.2839089
H	-7.5300641	9.2119990	-0.1964751
N	-10.1565209	8.9308310	0.0791558
H	-10.6660123	6.3284241	0.2222877
H	-9.0104615	4.5153774	0.1224234
C	-9.8342915	10.1580069	0.6917907
C	-10.2326088	11.3588901	0.1084567
C	-9.9273956	12.5639839	0.7179075
C	-9.2107236	12.5916851	1.9054604
C	-8.8093667	11.3963930	2.4847044
C	-9.1241718	10.1864149	1.8903254
C	-11.4412061	8.7553638	-0.4730865
C	-12.5667838	9.2058147	0.2129529
C	-13.8273104	9.0463904	-0.3370249
C	-13.9857179	8.4253844	-1.5675404
C	-12.8655305	7.9710695	-2.2488415
C	-11.6003220	8.1401186	-1.7128960
H	-10.7853211	11.3384348	-0.8229348
H	-10.2425294	13.4904005	0.2516478
H	-8.9678741	13.5365392	2.3762259

H	-8.2572862	11.4026666	3.4175117
H	-8.8204252	9.2536900	2.3500332
H	-12.4440375	9.6840905	1.1771690
H	-14.6944023	9.4001789	0.2088192
H	-14.9738095	8.2970834	-1.9925319
H	-12.9739531	7.4921598	-3.2151633
H	-10.7253232	7.7956336	-2.2507455
C	6.9260356	-7.1637173	-0.1679638
C	7.8541996	-8.1817005	-0.1210912
C	9.2154135	-7.8992128	0.0215040
C	9.6153758	-6.5628034	0.1058658
C	8.6864001	-5.5461772	0.0471929
H	5.8748986	-7.3980235	-0.2839089
H	7.5300641	-9.2119990	-0.1964751
N	10.1565209	-8.9308310	0.0791558
H	10.6660123	-6.3284241	0.2222877
H	9.0104615	-4.5153774	0.1224234
C	9.8342915	-10.1580069	0.6917907
C	10.2326088	-11.3588901	0.1084567
C	9.9273956	-12.5639839	0.7179075
C	9.2107236	-12.5916851	1.9054604
C	8.8093667	-11.3963930	2.4847044
C	9.1241718	-10.1864149	1.8903254
C	11.4412061	-8.7553638	-0.4730865
C	12.5667838	-9.2058147	0.2129529
C	13.8273104	-9.0463904	-0.3370249
C	13.9857179	-8.4253844	-1.5675404
C	12.8655305	-7.9710695	-2.2488415
C	11.6003220	-8.1401186	-1.7128960
H	10.7853211	-11.3384348	-0.8229348
H	10.2425294	-13.4904005	0.2516478
H	8.9678741	-13.5365392	2.3762259
H	8.2572862	-11.4026666	3.4175117
H	8.8204252	-9.2536900	2.3500332
H	12.4440375	-9.6840905	1.1771690
H	14.6944023	-9.4001789	0.2088192
H	14.9738095	-8.2970834	-1.9925319
H	12.9739531	-7.4921598	-3.2151633
H	10.7253232	-7.7956336	-2.2507455

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bisbtz-v

C	0.6231584	-0.3633390	0.0796946
S	0.6181472	-2.1059244	0.0851077
C	2.3434309	-2.0664599	0.0771737
C	2.7827559	-0.7245632	0.0707742
N	1.7856361	0.2086071	0.0733434
C	4.1531698	-0.4521663	0.0603306
C	5.0432222	-1.4976183	0.0559215
C	4.6032843	-2.8406517	0.0627616
C	3.2377999	-3.1239785	0.0741240
H	4.4897721	0.5770402	0.0551784
H	6.1088120	-1.3066839	0.0474416
C	5.5490778	-3.8921155	0.0559320
H	2.9015901	-4.1526779	0.0782125
C	-0.6231584	0.3633390	0.0796946
S	-0.6181472	2.1059244	0.0851077

C	-2.3434309	2.0664599	0.0771737
C	-2.7827559	0.7245632	0.0707742
N	-1.7856361	-0.2086071	0.0733434
C	-4.1531698	0.4521663	0.0603306
C	-5.0432222	1.4976183	0.0559215
C	-4.6032843	2.8406517	0.0627616
C	-3.2377999	3.1239785	0.0741240
H	-4.4897721	-0.5770402	0.0551784
H	-6.1088120	1.3066839	0.0474416
C	-5.5490778	3.8921155	0.0559320
H	-2.9015901	4.1526779	0.0782125
C	-6.3628522	4.7874680	0.0472866
C	-7.3139650	5.8325237	0.0341519
C	6.3628522	-4.7874680	0.0472866
C	7.3139650	-5.8325237	0.0341519
C	-6.9180465	7.1726944	0.1219188
C	-7.8441529	8.1925297	0.1036892
C	-9.2124981	7.9153554	0.0021503
C	-9.6135239	6.5768038	-0.0818875
C	-8.6835756	5.5605825	-0.0689768
H	-5.8626783	7.4067502	0.1921193
H	-7.5134897	9.2216084	0.1632863
N	-10.1496908	8.9430923	-0.0156513
H	-10.6676574	6.3415771	-0.1537452
H	-9.0129768	4.5302353	-0.1273026
C	-9.9000736	10.1631127	0.6491182
C	-10.1732463	11.3773020	0.0192107
C	-9.9526588	12.5726239	0.6694792
C	-9.4354303	12.5872283	1.9636312
C	-9.1548829	11.3819469	2.5980350
C	-9.4002422	10.1831456	1.9436270
C	-11.3769050	8.7902002	-0.6967291
C	-12.5725705	9.1749556	-0.0903585
C	-13.7724734	9.0464816	-0.7568090
C	-13.8116122	8.5125055	-2.0436212
C	-12.6250623	8.1221357	-2.6548912
C	-11.4197892	8.2749710	-1.9845844
H	-10.5700847	11.3738579	-0.9889144
H	-10.1641617	13.5179193	0.1846892
O	-9.2425492	13.8070557	2.5156752
H	-8.7603238	11.3600448	3.6047756
H	-9.1915384	9.2463445	2.4465915
H	-12.5505032	9.5850859	0.9122106
H	-14.7036376	9.3443975	-0.2903709
O	-15.0350756	8.4136995	-2.6121629
H	-12.6214704	7.7123825	-3.6558151
H	-10.4964838	7.9801584	-2.4690890
C	6.9180465	-7.1726944	0.1219188
C	7.8441529	-8.1925297	0.1036892
C	9.2124981	-7.9153554	0.0021503
C	9.6135239	-6.5768038	-0.0818875
C	8.6835756	-5.5605825	-0.0689768
H	5.8626783	-7.4067502	0.1921193
H	7.5134897	-9.2216084	0.1632863
N	10.1496908	-8.9430923	-0.0156513
H	10.6676574	-6.3415771	-0.1537452
H	9.0129768	-4.5302353	-0.1273026

C	9.9000736	-10.1631127	0.6491182
C	10.1732463	-11.3773020	0.0192107
C	9.9526588	-12.5726239	0.6694792
C	9.4354303	-12.5872283	1.9636312
C	9.1548829	-11.3819469	2.5980350
C	9.4002422	-10.1831456	1.9436270
C	11.3769050	-8.7902002	-0.6967291
C	12.5725705	-9.1749556	-0.0903585
C	13.7724734	-9.0464816	-0.7568090
C	13.8116122	-8.5125055	-2.0436212
C	12.6250623	-8.1221357	-2.6548912
C	11.4197892	-8.2749710	-1.9845844
H	10.5700847	-11.3738579	-0.9889144
H	10.1641617	-13.5179193	0.1846892
O	9.2425492	-13.8070557	2.5156752
H	8.7603238	-11.3600448	3.6047756
H	9.1915384	-9.2463445	2.4465915
H	12.5505032	-9.5850859	0.9122106
H	14.7036376	-9.3443975	-0.2903709
O	15.0350756	-8.4136995	-2.6121629
H	12.6214704	-7.7123825	-3.6558151
H	10.4964838	-7.9801584	-2.4690890
C	-8.7263086	13.8592617	3.8220886
H	-8.6452621	14.9146484	4.0760159
H	-9.3937162	13.3671229	4.5380887
H	-7.7345403	13.3974654	3.8809618
C	-15.1108944	7.8848181	-3.9123149
H	-16.1655379	7.8877792	-4.1816575
H	-14.5545747	8.4987757	-4.6290845
H	-14.7321689	6.8575277	-3.9508039
C	8.7263086	-13.8592617	3.8220886
H	8.6452621	-14.9146484	4.0760159
H	9.3937162	-13.3671229	4.5380887
H	7.7345403	-13.3974654	3.8809618
C	15.1108944	-7.8848181	-3.9123149
H	16.1655379	-7.8877792	-4.1816575
H	14.5545747	-8.4987757	-4.6290845
H	14.7321689	-6.8575277	-3.9508039

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bisbtz-VI

S	1.3005046	1.7688692	-0.1051933
C	-0.0883750	0.7158162	-0.1043622
N	-1.2475008	1.2957504	-0.1025125
C	-2.1508410	3.5847537	-0.0994286
C	-1.8555272	4.9244425	-0.0975383
C	-0.5242733	5.3979328	-0.0952560
C	0.5169408	4.4724738	-0.1006109
C	0.2242473	3.1170876	-0.1020941
C	-1.1071262	2.6536141	-0.1005839
H	-3.1748216	3.2321736	-0.1022659
H	-2.6706144	5.6369799	-0.1031242
H	1.5437281	4.8200267	-0.1009226
C	-0.1896892	6.8116709	-0.0876589
H	0.8757740	7.0218573	-0.1278316
C	-1.0489899	7.8399104	-0.0249675
H	-2.1133462	7.6297399	0.0391410

C	-0.7193788	9.2530469	-0.0193590
C	0.5786319	9.7521056	-0.1826298
C	0.8369203	11.1048364	-0.1686639
C	-0.1960894	12.0288665	0.0203419
C	-1.4942129	11.5468742	0.1837655
C	-1.7424950	10.1892112	0.1551088
H	1.4041144	9.0697637	-0.3474625
H	1.8486705	11.4638793	-0.3106188
H	-2.3080370	12.2454000	0.3329963
H	-2.7597224	9.8361727	0.2894901
N	0.0693917	13.4027905	0.0372121
C	-0.8630878	14.3137598	-0.4955081
C	-1.1398264	15.5062443	0.1694104
C	-2.0490687	16.4051882	-0.3612970
C	-2.7049765	16.1248246	-1.5510614
C	-2.4336199	14.9352570	-2.2117830
C	-1.5147450	14.0379273	-1.6958376
H	-0.6341924	15.7225925	1.1027971
H	-2.2555491	17.3278910	0.1688528
H	-3.4207103	16.8273634	-1.9603483
H	-2.9315003	14.7074674	-3.1473648
H	-1.2959514	13.1144832	-2.2182935
C	1.2671599	13.8877656	0.5965324
C	1.7627645	13.3515672	1.7836687
C	2.9445185	13.8297472	2.3239687
C	3.6399596	14.8563977	1.7013416
C	3.1421194	15.3977262	0.5246527
C	1.9690024	14.9155783	-0.0303578
H	1.2151168	12.5578358	2.2768463
H	3.3168485	13.4040213	3.2486761
H	4.5613383	15.2318261	2.1295905
H	3.6783356	16.1956314	0.0239512
H	1.5854225	15.3327935	-0.9534080
S	-1.3005046	-1.7688692	-0.1051933
C	0.0883750	-0.7158162	-0.1043622
N	1.2475008	-1.2957504	-0.1025125
C	2.1508410	-3.5847537	-0.0994286
C	1.8555272	-4.9244425	-0.0975383
C	0.5242733	-5.3979328	-0.0952560
C	-0.5169408	-4.4724738	-0.1006109
C	-0.2242473	-3.1170876	-0.1020941
C	1.1071262	-2.6536141	-0.1005839
H	3.1748216	-3.2321736	-0.1022659
H	2.6706144	-5.6369799	-0.1031242
H	-1.5437281	-4.8200267	-0.1009226
C	0.1896892	-6.8116709	-0.0876589
H	-0.8757740	-7.0218573	-0.1278316
C	1.0489899	-7.8399104	-0.0249675
H	2.1133462	-7.6297399	0.0391410
C	0.7193788	-9.2530469	-0.0193590
C	-0.5786319	-9.7521056	-0.1826298
C	-0.8369203	-11.1048364	-0.1686639
C	0.1960894	-12.0288665	0.0203419
C	1.4942129	-11.5468742	0.1837655
C	1.7424950	-10.1892112	0.1551088
H	-1.4041144	-9.0697637	-0.3474625
H	-1.8486705	-11.4638793	-0.3106188

H	2.3080370	-12.2454000	0.3329963
H	2.7597224	-9.8361727	0.2894901
N	-0.0693917	-13.4027905	0.0372121
C	-1.2671599	-13.8877656	0.5965324
C	-1.7627645	-13.3515672	1.7836687
C	-2.9445185	-13.8297472	2.3239687
C	-3.6399596	-14.8563977	1.7013416
C	-3.1421194	-15.3977262	0.5246527
C	-1.9690024	-14.9155783	-0.0303578
H	-1.2151168	-12.5578358	2.2768463
H	-3.3168485	-13.4040213	3.2486761
H	-4.5613383	-15.2318261	2.1295905
H	-3.6783356	-16.1956314	0.0239512
H	-1.5854225	-15.3327935	-0.9534080
C	0.8630878	-14.3137598	-0.4955081
C	1.1398264	-15.5062443	0.1694104
C	2.0490687	-16.4051882	-0.3612970
C	2.7049765	-16.1248246	-1.5510614
C	2.4336199	-14.9352570	-2.2117830
C	1.5147450	-14.0379273	-1.6958376
H	0.6341924	-15.7225925	1.1027971
H	2.2555491	-17.3278910	0.1688528
H	3.4207103	-16.8273634	-1.9603483
H	2.9315003	-14.7074674	-3.1473648
H	1.2959514	-13.1144832	-2.2182935

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btz-VI

S	1.4594513	-8.5951129	-0.2677318
C	0.0823477	-9.6483955	-0.1944671
N	-1.0709774	-9.0846096	-0.1061821
C	-1.9770627	-6.7927929	-0.0036794
C	-1.6889566	-5.4504479	0.0009431
C	-0.3639256	-4.9693983	-0.0783138
C	0.6779466	-5.8884718	-0.1650291
C	0.3891503	-7.2454788	-0.1706247
C	-0.9333835	-7.7176118	-0.0902362
H	-2.9973995	-7.1507453	0.0574162
H	-2.5060580	-4.7430871	0.0663325
H	1.7010673	-5.5358010	-0.2269602
C	-0.0330585	-3.5533871	-0.0742922
H	1.0305441	-3.3421364	-0.1459893
C	-0.8903689	-2.5262146	0.0116259
H	-1.9534640	-2.7356965	0.0961885
C	-0.5592415	-1.1124588	0.0112370
C	0.7389635	-0.6156340	-0.1554885
C	0.9985808	0.7370057	-0.1495508
C	-0.0333021	1.6626462	0.0347023
C	-1.3313868	1.1832126	0.2029413
C	-1.5809613	-0.1746439	0.1827258
H	1.5640920	-1.2997721	-0.3147615
H	2.0107864	1.0943546	-0.2930873
H	-2.1442980	1.8836591	0.3489247
H	-2.5982270	-0.5263985	0.3204048
N	0.2340764	3.0368903	0.0431783
C	-0.6908598	3.9438851	-0.5078835
C	-0.9694866	5.1452326	0.1400777

C	-1.8718489	6.0399631	-0.4089752
C	-2.5194259	5.7466860	-1.6001212
C	-2.2467042	4.5480982	-2.2435861
C	-1.3343049	3.6548845	-1.7095144
H	-0.4712670	5.3717538	1.0751000
H	-2.0797292	6.9699364	0.1079204
H	-3.2299448	6.4461337	-2.0237178
H	-2.7383220	4.3098199	-3.1799517
H	-1.1142016	2.7242754	-2.2186584
C	1.4279893	3.5226634	0.6092950
C	1.9100519	2.9943609	1.8055031
C	3.0889447	3.4714583	2.3527506
C	3.7950677	4.4893463	1.7278997
C	3.3108999	5.0227223	0.5420071
C	2.1407184	4.5414832	-0.0198891
H	1.3538879	2.2074523	2.3002449
H	3.4506164	3.0519604	3.2846025
H	4.7142592	4.8641005	2.1615179
H	3.8558135	5.8136184	0.0394076
H	1.7684760	4.9521810	-0.9505541
H	0.2244346	-10.7214892	-0.2237012

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bpy-VI

C	0.5612895	0.4840364	-0.2059182
N	0.2471984	1.7796919	-0.2259950
C	1.2493251	2.6506723	-0.2251460
C	2.5847088	2.2979355	-0.2019313
C	2.9291071	0.9429361	-0.1776019
C	1.8754887	0.0321823	-0.1821092
H	0.9678709	3.7001899	-0.2432989
H	3.3390138	3.0745818	-0.2006029
C	4.2952665	0.4451375	-0.1435151
H	2.0561771	-1.0350228	-0.1660821
C	-0.5612895	-0.4840364	-0.2059182
C	-1.8754887	-0.0321823	-0.1821092
C	-2.9291071	-0.9429361	-0.1776019
C	-2.5847088	-2.2979355	-0.2019313
C	-1.2493251	-2.6506723	-0.2251460
N	-0.2471984	-1.7796919	-0.2259950
H	-2.0561771	1.0350228	-0.1660821
C	-4.2952665	-0.4451375	-0.1435151
H	-3.3390138	-3.0745818	-0.2006029
H	-0.9678709	-3.7001899	-0.2432989
C	5.4082458	1.1916907	-0.1392875
C	6.7794366	0.7181259	-0.0988462
C	7.8199229	1.6498063	-0.0530708
C	9.1443188	1.2636843	0.0025049
C	9.4833458	-0.0889773	0.0019435
C	8.4527331	-1.0334223	-0.0560783
C	7.1349723	-0.6362324	-0.1004799
H	7.5779002	2.7076225	-0.0443092
H	9.9273866	2.0101789	0.0485783
N	10.8207997	-0.4960008	0.0539231
H	8.7010550	-2.0874623	-0.0691026
H	6.3661027	-1.3977678	-0.1551081
C	11.8192234	0.2613862	-0.5890997

C	13.0390483	0.4971040	0.0411402
C	14.0230651	1.2314659	-0.5984508
C	13.8025220	1.7528803	-1.8649493
C	12.5857302	1.5237931	-2.4910930
C	11.6021701	0.7777251	-1.8649019
C	11.1840499	-1.6537260	0.7682137
C	12.1356625	-2.5293207	0.2494581
C	12.5007227	-3.6608760	0.9580532
C	11.9147932	-3.9452086	2.1830605
C	10.9627795	-3.0772528	2.6977683
C	10.6036836	-1.9349398	2.0033276
H	13.2096227	0.0968602	1.0332249
H	14.9666306	1.4078439	-0.0948106
H	14.5724114	2.3319685	-2.3601852
H	12.4029927	1.9171864	-3.4845183
H	10.6566648	0.5901121	-2.3593826
H	12.5877297	-2.3128820	-0.7109334
H	13.2415715	-4.3333269	0.5409602
H	12.1980609	-4.8349913	2.7321180
H	10.5028349	-3.2822656	3.6577104
H	9.8687009	-1.2524983	2.4124776
C	-5.4082458	-1.1916907	-0.1392875
C	-6.7794366	-0.7181259	-0.0988462
C	-7.1349723	0.6362324	-0.1004799
C	-8.4527331	1.0334223	-0.0560783
C	-9.4833458	0.0889773	0.0019435
C	-9.1443188	-1.2636843	0.0025049
C	-7.8199229	-1.6498063	-0.0530708
H	-6.3661027	1.3977678	-0.1551081
H	-8.7010550	2.0874623	-0.0691026
N	-10.8207997	0.4960008	0.0539231
H	-9.9273866	-2.0101789	0.0485783
H	-7.5779002	-2.7076225	-0.0443092
C	-11.8192234	-0.2613862	-0.5890997
C	-13.0390483	-0.4971040	0.0411402
C	-14.0230651	-1.2314659	-0.5984508
C	-13.8025220	-1.7528803	-1.8649493
C	-12.5857302	-1.5237931	-2.4910930
C	-11.6021701	-0.7777251	-1.8649019
C	-11.1840499	1.6537260	0.7682137
C	-12.1356625	2.5293207	0.2494581
C	-12.5007227	3.6608760	0.9580532
C	-11.9147932	3.9452086	2.1830605
C	-10.9627795	3.0772528	2.6977683
C	-10.6036836	1.9349398	2.0033276
H	-13.2096227	-0.0968602	1.0332249
H	-14.9666306	-1.4078439	-0.0948106
H	-14.5724114	-2.3319685	-2.3601852
H	-12.4029927	-1.9171864	-3.4845183
H	-10.6566648	-0.5901121	-2.3593826
H	-12.5877297	2.3128820	-0.7109334
H	-13.2415715	4.3333269	0.5409602
H	-12.1980609	4.8349913	2.7321180
H	-10.5028349	3.2822656	3.6577104
H	-9.8687009	1.2524983	2.4124776
H	4.3792076	-0.6375390	-0.1143622
H	5.3085035	2.2741283	-0.1632925

H	-4.3792076	0.6375390	-0.1143622
H	-5.3085035	-2.2741283	-0.1632925

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ReCl(CO)₃ bisbtz-I

Re	-1.1512168	2.2843472	0.0000000
Cl	-3.1396378	0.8535360	0.0000000
C	-1.8800478	3.4775905	1.3051994
O	-2.3167538	4.2057999	2.0794113
C	0.4641429	3.3074034	0.0000000
O	1.4304597	3.9359294	0.0000000
C	-1.8800478	3.4775905	-1.3051994
O	-2.3167538	4.2057999	-2.0794113
S	0.4551901	-1.6983254	1.7328607
C	-0.0101959	-0.3928152	0.7126785
N	-0.3711739	0.7082094	1.3327659
C	-0.2885094	0.5683622	2.6938680
C	-0.5839689	1.5284531	3.6628788
C	-0.4437518	1.2062455	4.9888809
C	0.0031485	-0.0662621	5.4025626
C	0.3101849	-1.0294203	4.4459065
C	0.1513244	-0.7013762	3.1114947
H	-0.9384728	2.5064380	3.3721065
H	-0.6915153	1.9407932	5.7437432
H	0.6599373	-2.0078249	4.7467323
S	0.4551901	-1.6983254	-1.7328607
C	-0.0101959	-0.3928152	-0.7126785
N	-0.3711739	0.7082094	-1.3327659
C	-0.2885094	0.5683622	-2.6938680
C	-0.5839689	1.5284531	-3.6628788
C	-0.4437518	1.2062455	-4.9888809
C	0.0031485	-0.0662621	-5.4025626
C	0.3101849	-1.0294203	-4.4459065
C	0.1513244	-0.7013762	-3.1114947
H	-0.9384728	2.5064380	-3.3721065
H	-0.6915153	1.9407932	-5.7437432
H	0.6599373	-2.0078249	-4.7467323
N	0.1237414	-0.3529887	6.7596255
C	-0.0706552	-1.6679985	7.2350333
C	-1.1619055	-2.4191137	6.8044898
C	-1.3486933	-3.7061148	7.2785739
C	-0.4632280	-4.2535135	8.1965863
C	0.6176641	-3.5015922	8.6327278
C	0.8203527	-2.2187603	8.1519444
H	-1.8614094	-1.9867319	6.0989214
H	-2.2036390	-4.2792454	6.9391611
H	-0.6172482	-5.2579245	8.5717423
H	1.3179564	-3.9192551	9.3466646
H	1.6664313	-1.6318684	8.4887444
C	0.5030888	0.6531994	7.6742035
C	-0.1328585	0.7449368	8.9098036
C	0.2465966	1.7214438	9.8146479
C	1.2508997	2.6247297	9.4958272
C	1.8813765	2.5360569	8.2632364
C	1.5194679	1.5516369	7.3588470
H	-0.9224752	0.0446065	9.1538192
H	-0.2573667	1.7844784	10.7719720

H	1.5401803	3.3920993	10.2033780
H	2.6727046	3.2302748	8.0057990
H	2.0217491	1.4751689	6.4019227
N	0.1237414	-0.3529887	-6.7596255
C	-0.0706552	-1.6679985	-7.2350333
C	-1.1619055	-2.4191137	-6.8044898
C	-1.3486933	-3.7061148	-7.2785739
C	-0.4632280	-4.2535135	-8.1965863
C	0.6176641	-3.5015922	-8.6327278
C	0.8203527	-2.2187603	-8.1519444
H	-1.8614094	-1.9867319	-6.0989214
H	-2.2036390	-4.2792454	-6.9391611
H	-0.6172482	-5.2579245	-8.5717423
H	1.3179564	-3.9192551	-9.3466646
H	1.6664313	-1.6318684	-8.4887444
C	0.5030888	0.6531994	-7.6742035
C	-0.1328585	0.7449368	-8.9098036
C	0.2465966	1.7214438	-9.8146479
C	1.2508997	2.6247297	-9.4958272
C	1.8813765	2.5360569	-8.2632364
C	1.5194679	1.5516369	-7.3588470
H	-0.9224752	0.0446065	-9.1538192
H	-0.2573667	1.7844784	-10.7719720
H	1.5401803	3.3920993	-10.2033780
H	2.6727046	3.2302748	-8.0057990
H	2.0217491	1.4751689	-6.4019227

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